

UNIVERSITY OF BAGHDAD

**AN ANALYTIC STUDY OF THE DIFFICULTIES
FACED BY IRAQI EFL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS
IN THE USE OF THE ENGLISH PASSIVE
STRUCTURE**

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بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

وَقُلْ رَبِّ زِدْنِي عِلْمًا

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TO MY FAMILY

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims at finding out the difficulties encountered by Iraqi college students of English as a foreign language by using the English passive structure at both the recognition and production levels. The work has been based on the following hypotheses:-

(1) Iraqi college students encounter difficulties in using the English passive structure. The difficulties follow the ascending order:-

(a) the transformed Obj.

(b) the verb phrase

(2) Explicitness is positively proportioned to the subjects' performance on the passive structure at both levels, that is the subjects' performance when they are explicitly directed to use the structure is better than that when they are not, in certain recognition and production item tests, and guided written compositions.

(3) The students' avoidance of using the structure in the written compositions is positively correlated with the difficulty inherent in the use of the structure, manifested by the subjects' results in the recognition and production item tests.

(4) There is growth in competence in the performance of both groups under study at both the recognition and production levels. Furthermore, there is an increase in the number of the passive structure instances used in the written compositions of Iraqi students of English as a foreign language at the advanced years in comparison with that used at the early years at the university level.

(5) Errors committed by using the verb phrase, that are attributable to interlingual transfer are more than those related to other strategies affecting the students' performance on this area.

After a thorough survey of the literature, a test has been constructed to investigate the hypotheses mentioned above. Following a pilot test, the test has been administered to sixty students (males and females), thirty students from the second year, and thirty students from the fourth year, from the Department of English, College of Languages, University of Baghdad. In analysing the students' responses to the test items, and written compositions, Z-test, correlation coefficient reliability, t-test, and analysis of variance have been manipulated. In the light of this analysis, the following conclusions have been drawn:-

(1) Iraqi students encounter difficulties by using the English passive structure. The difficulties are felt to be much more in recognising the transformed Obj. and the verb phrase than in producing them when they are explicitly directed to use the structure. However, the difficulty is felt to be much more in producing the verb phrase when they are inexplicitly directed to use the structure than in recognising it for both initials and advanced students of English as a foreign language at the university level.

Furthermore, the difficulty encountered by the use of the verb phrase at both the recognition and production levels, when they are explicitly and inexplicitly directed to produce the verb phrase, is much more than that encountered by the use of transformed Obj. at both levels. However, with respect to the advanced students' performance, the difficulty encountered by producing transformed Obj. of the passive construction types under study is felt to be much

more than that on the verb phrase when the students are explicitly directed to produce the structure.

(2) The students' performance in recognising and producing the verb phrase when they are explicitly directed to use the structure is better than that in recognising and producing it when they are not, in certain recognition, production item tests, and guided written compositions.

(3) Avoidance of the passive structure in the written compositions of students is not correlated with the difficulty actualised by their performance on the recognition and production item tests. Rather, avoidance is affected by certain psychological variables, such as confidence in one's limited knowledge about a certain structure.

(4) There is a significant development in the performance of the second and fourth year students in using the passive structure at both levels.

(5) Negative interlingual transfer, that is interference, is found to be responsible for the major part of errors committed by using the verb phrase, which consists in using the active instead of the passive, and in omitting the Aux. *BE* that precedes the past participle.

Finally, on the basis of the findings, some recommendations for teaching English as a foreign language are outlined, and some suggestions for further research are stated.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS

Act	Active
Adv.	Adverb(ial)
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
AP	Adjectival Phrase
Asp.	Aspect
Aux.	Auxiliary
BA	Baghdadi Arabic
Comp(s)	Composition(s) One, Two, etc.
Cor. Coef.	Correlation Coefficient
e	empty element
Gn	Group One, Group Two
GB	Government Binding
I	Inflection Constituent
L ₁	The first language (native, source)
L ₂	The second language (foreign, target)
M(s)	Modal(s)
Man Adv(s)	Manner Adverb(ial)(s)
NP(s)	Noun Phrase(s)
Obj(s)	Object(s)
Pass(s)	Passive(s)
Perf.	Perfect
PP	Prepositional Phrase

Prod.	Production
Prog.	Progressive
Pr. Phr.	Predicative Phrase
Qn	Question One, Question Two, etc.
Recog.	Recognition
Sn	Subject One, subject Two (= Testee), etc.
S ^l	Sentence bar
S	Sentence
Subj(s)	Subject(s)
TGG	Transformational Generative Grammar
TL	Target Language
Tns	Tense
V ^l	Verb bar
V	Verb
VP(s)	Verb Phrase(s)
△	empty node
Ho	null hypothesis
—\	is written as
>	is larger than
*	ungrammatical sentence
?	unacceptable sentence

KEY TO PHONETIC SYMBOLS

The symbols used in the present study are as follows:-

1. Baghdadi Arabic Consonants

[b]	as in	[baárda]	“cold”
[t]	as in	[tahriír]	“making free”
[k]	as in	[kísar]	“he broke”
[ʔ]	as in	[ʔákal]	“he ate”
[h]	as in	[haznaán]	“sad”
[n]	as in	[níhmi]	“we protect”
[l]	as in	[leéš]	“why?”
[r]	as in	[ráhhab]	“we welcomed”

2. Baghdadi Arabic Vowels

[i]	as in	[kítab]	“he wrote”
[a]	as in	[dárub]	“road”

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Problem

“Voice is a verb form or particular syntactic construction indicating certain relationships between the subject and object of a verb.” (Hartmann and Stork, 1972:251-2). English has both Act. and Pass. voice sentences. The Pass. is a term used in the grammatical analysis of voice to refer to a sentence, clause, or verb form, where the grammatical Subj. is typically the ‘recepient’ or ‘goal’ of the action denoted by the verb, e.g.:-

(1.1) a. The boy *wrote* the letter.

b. The letter *was written* by the boy.

The idea of moving the noun (or NP) from the Obj. position to the Subj. position is agreed upon by all grammarians, in that the Act. Obj. is moved into the Subj. position, and the Act. Subj. is made the agent introduced by *by*. Moreover, the VP adds a form of Aux. with the past participle of the verb (Quirk et al., 1985:159).

However, Iraqi EFL students face difficulties in using the Pass. structure in English. More specifically, they encounter difficulties in recognising and producing the structure. As, to the best of the researcher’s knowledge, the extent of Iraqi EFL students’ use, and the amount of growth in competence in recognising and producing the Pass. have not been carried out yet, the present study is expected to fill such a gap.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The study aims at:-

- (1) Investigating the difficulties that Iraqi EFL students might encounter in the area of the Pass. structure at both the Recog. and Prod. levels in the domain of:-
 - (a) the VP form and transformed Obj., and
 - (b) the Pass. VP when they are explicitly directed to perform the structure; and when they are left to their free discretion about it,
- (2) Investigating the avoidance of using the Pass. structure that both groups under study display in their written communication,
- (3) Investigating the growth in competence of Iraqi EFL students under study in recognising and producing the Pass., and
- (4) Investigating the type of errors committed by the students in the use of the Pass. VP, and the strategies that Iraqi EFL students resort to when the students commit them.

1.3 The Hypotheses

It is hypothesised that:-

- (1) Iraqi EFL students encounter difficulty in the area of the Pass. structure at both the Recog. and Prod. levels. The difficulty is expected to follow the ascending order:-
 - (a) the transformed Obj.
 - (b) the VP form
- (2) Errors are fewer in number when the Pass. VP structure is explicitly elicited than those elicited when the Pass. VP structure is inexplicit in certain item tests and guided written Comps. In other

words, errors committed in the area of the Pass. VP structure are inversely proportioned to the amount of explicitness of the structure elicited differently in various elicitation techniques.

(3) Avoidance of the Pass. structure in the guided written Comps. is positively correlated with the difficulty encountered in recognising and producing the Pass. structure in the Recog. and Prod. item tests.

(4) Students at the early years of the university level make more errors in using the Pass. structure than those at the advanced years.

(5) Errors committed by the use of the Pass. VP pertaining to interlingual transfer exceed those pertaining to other strategies (such as intralingual transfer and context of learning). This is due to the negative influence of the mother tongue of Iraqi EFL students on the TL.

1.4 The Procedures

The procedures to be followed in this study can be summarised as follows:-

(1) Surveying the available literature in order to provide a comprehensive account of the Pass. structure in English.

(2) Designing and administering a number of tests to two groups of Iraqi EFL students, i.e. thirty students from the second year, and thirty students from the fourth year (males and females) from the Department of English, College of Languages, University of Baghdad.

The test consists of the Recog. and Prod. item tests, and guided written Comps. Each is designed in order to fulfil certain

objectives. The items are designed in a way which covers an exhaustive account of the types of the Pass. constructions under study.

- (3) Analysing and discussing the results of the test.
- (4) Drawing conclusions, and making some recommendations and suggestions for further pedagogical research.

The model adopted in this study is eclectic. It is a combination of Chomsky's (1957, 1965) theories in TGG, and recent works within Generative Grammars, represented by the GB theory, in addition to Quirk et al.'s (1985) treatment of the Pass. structure in English.

1.5 Data of the Study

The data of the study consist of the students' responses elicited by the various types of tests that are designed on the basis of the theoretical survey.

1.6 Limits of the Study

The study is limited to investigating the affirmative Pass. sentences. The Pass. constructions under study are limited to finite clauses containing VPs whose Act. versions are followed by Objs. that can undergo the application of the NP-Movement rule. The Aux. to be investigated comprises verb to *Be*, which occurs in the Simple Present/Past Tns. Asp. and Ms, that may come into combination with Tns. under Aux., are excluded. The change that is traced includes one direction: Act. into Pass., and not the other way round.

The sample of the study is limited to Iraqi EFL students. It comprises sixty students: thirty students from the second year, and

thirty students from the fourth year from the Department of English, College of Languages, University of Baghdad. The influence of the native language upon the performance of the subject under study is limited to the colloquial BA, and not any other dialects of the Arabic language.

1.7 Value of the Study

The investigation to be undertaken in this study has both theoretical and practical values.

Theoretically, the study is useful for researchers and teachers as it investigates the Pass. structure in English within TGG, and the subsequent works within the GB theory.

Practically, the study is useful for teachers in that it identifies the problems that students may encounter in the domain of the Pass. structure in English, so that teachers could place much emphasis upon them while teaching English. For students, the study could direct their attention to the difficulties they face if they use the Pass. structure. Identification of the problems and their reasons could serve textbook writers and syllabus designers in that they provide remedial exercises and drills that help students avoid committing errors in the areas identified.

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

OF PASSIVISATION

2.1 Patterns of the Passive Verb Phrase¹

Pass VP patterns are classified in terms of the combinations of the Aux elements with the passivised verb. The constituent Aux includes *BE* and Tns, which can either be present or past. Other elements of Aux, like M., Perf., and Prog., may be used wherever and whenever needed in each pattern. The first element of these combinations which is to the right of Tns carries Tns; and *Be* can function as a linking verb. *Be* is referred to as “Pass. Aux verb” (Burton-Roberts, 1986:124).

The Pass. VP patterns are classified as follows:-

(1) The passive tense pattern, which consists of the constituent Aux that comprises Tns and *Be* accompanied by the past participle, as in the following example:

- (2.1) a. John $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \textit{reads} \\ \textit{read} \end{array} \right\}$ the book.
b. The book $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \textit{is} \\ \textit{was} \end{array} \right\}$ *read* by John.

(2) The passive modal pattern. This pattern is constructed by the constituent Aux, which consists of Tns + M + *Be*, accompanied

- (2.2) a. John $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \textit{will} \\ \textit{would} \end{array} \right\}$ *clean* my room.
b. My room $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \textit{will} \\ \textit{would} \end{array} \right\}$ *be cleaned* by John.

with the past participle. Ms are like *will, shall, may, can,* etc.

(3) The passive perfect pattern. The Perf. constituents in English are the Aux *has*, or *have*, accompanied by the past participle abstract ending *-en*. The pattern consists of the Aux which includes Tns +

$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \textit{has} + \textit{-en} \\ \textit{have} \\ \textit{had} \end{array} \right\} + \textit{Be}$, accompanied with the past participle. The Pass

VP is constructed by affixing Tns to *has*, or *have*; and affixing *-en* to *Be*.

(2.3) a. The scorpion $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \textit{has} \\ \textit{had} \end{array} \right\} \textit{stung}$ her.

b. She $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \textit{has} \\ \textit{had} \end{array} \right\} \textit{been stung}$ by the scorpion.

(5) The passive progressive pattern. The English Prog. consists of two elements: *Be* + *-ing*. This pattern is represented by Tns + *Be* + *-ing* + *Be*, accompanied by the past participle. Tns is affixed to the first element Prog., i.e. *Be*; while the second element, i.e. *-ing*, is affixed to the Pass Aux *Be* resulting in Pass. sentences like the following:-

- (2.5) a. They $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} are \\ were \end{array} \right\}$ *building* new factories.
 b. New factories $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} are \\ were \end{array} \right\}$ *being built* by them.

As for the present work, only the Pass Tns pattern will be tackled. The relation between the Aux. elements and the past participle of the sentence (2.1) is illustrated in the diagram below.

Figure (2.1) The Deep Structure of the Active-Passive Tense Pattern Based on Chomsky's (1965:129) Model.

2.2 Transformational Passive Types

Radford (1988:420-35) distinguishes between verbal and adjectival Pass. The former involves the application of NP-Movement to the direct Obj. NPs, double Objs., predicative complements (small clauses), infinitival complements with Subjs. (exceptional clauses), idiom chunk NPs, and Objs. of prepositions, (for a detailed discussion about the latter, i.e., adjectival or lexical Pass., see Wasow, 1977:342-360).

These types, i.e. Pass of double Obj. constructions, accusative Subj. Passs., Passs. of idiom chunk, Passs. of *help* and *thank*, and Pass. followed by predicative expressions, like a *fool*, or *president*, have been analysed as requiring a transformational derivation, and accordingly, they should never occur in the adjectival environments. Wasow (1977:343) uses four diagnostics for adjectives as evidence for the lexical derivation of Pass: (1) prenominal position, (2) appearance as complements to verbs, like *act*, *look*, and *seem*, (3) prefixation with *un-*, and (4) degree modification by *very* (without *much*). Consider the following examples:-

(2.6) *The (widely) *believed* to be a communist man turned out to be an FBI agent.

(2.7) *John $\left. \begin{array}{l} \textit{looks} \\ \textit{acts} \\ \textit{seems} \end{array} \right\}$ *told* the bad news.

(2.8) *The offer *was untaken* advantage of

(2.9) I *was very *(much) helped* by your comments.

Apart from the verbal types of Pass. mentioned above that require verbal Pass. operation, there is another type that is claimed to be transformational; though not verbal, and Radford (1988:420-33)

considers it to be verbal (transformational), that is referred to as “Pseudo-pass.” This type subsumes both prepositional Passs. and idiom chunk Passs., as long as the verbs and NPs can undergo Verb-Preposition Reanalysis rule (Hoekstra, 1984:208-9; Radford, 1988:428-31).

(2.10) The children *were badly looked after*.

(2.11) The boy *was taken* advantage of.

According to Quirk et al. (1985:167), these sentences are Pseudo-passs. as they do not have a clear correspondence with an Act. VP or Act. clause, and are remoted from the ideal Pass. which can be placed in direct correspondence with a unique Act. counterpart.

Thus, Pseudo-pass. types have been classified in terms of the direct/indirect application of the NP-Movement rule; or in terms of whether they have, or they do not have, corresponding Act. counterparts, into middle constructions, prepositional Pass., and idiom chunk Pass (Table (2.1) below).

Table (2.1) Transformational Passive Types

Verbal Passives	Direct Object Passives	Passives of Verbs Followed by Single Noun Phrases Passives of Verbs Followed by <i>that</i> -Clauses Passives of Verbs Followed by Non-Finite Clauses
		Passives of Double Objects Passives with Predicative Complements Passives Followed by Infinitival Complements with Subjects Passives of Causative Verbs and Verbs of Perception
Pseudo-passives		Middle Constructions Prepositional Passives Idiom Chunk Passives

Thomson and Martinet (1986:267-8) note that sentences of the type VP followed by the clause as the Obj. have two possible forms:-

- d. Mary *was expected* to have won.
- e. It *was expected* that Mary would win.

Quirk and Greenbaum (1973:361) distinguish another type where the direct Obj. that undergoes NP-Movement is a non-finite clause Obj. without an overt Subj, consisting of an infinitive verb preceded by *to*. In this type the implied Subj. is normally the Subj. of the superordinate clause, as in:-

(2.15) John *longed to* do homework.

Attention should be drawn to the fact that there is in general no Pass. for this type with the exception of a few verbs, such as *agree, arrange, decide*, and only if there is extraposition. This is shown in the following example:-

- (2.16) a. They *decided to* meet in London.
- b. It *was decided to* meet in London. (ibid.:363)

It is worth observing that passivisation is limited to applying to an Obj. NP, or clause (finite and non-finite) which is immediately adjacent to a verb. Moreover, the Obj. should be a complement; not an Adv. (Radford, 1988:432-3). In McCawley's (1988:81) terms:-

the V and the NP that is to be made into the subject must be VP-mates: the lowest VP node that dominates one of them, must also be the lowest VP that dominates the other. (Figure (2.2) below)

Consider the following sentences.

- (2.17) a. Many people *intend to* buy cars.
- b. *Cars *are intended to* buy by many people.

- (2.18) a. A bomb *exploded* outside City Hall.
 b. *City Hall *was exploded* outside by a bomb.

- (2.19) a. Few children *play* football.
 b. Football *is played* by few children.

In the first two cases, the verb and NP that would undergo NP-Movement are not in the same VP. In (2.17a), the NP *cars* is in the VP of *to buy cars*, that is embedded in the VP *intend to buy cars*, of which the verb *intend* is the head. In (2.18a), the NP *City Hall* is in the adverbial expression *outside City Hall*, outside the VP *exploded*. The ungrammatical cases are represented in figure (2.2a, and b) respectively. The grammatical sentence (2.19b) is represented in Figure (2.2c).

Figure (2.2) Conditions on NP-Movement

For the Pass. rule to apply, the V and NP should be under the same VP node. The following examples are presented to show that (2.20b) is grammatical as the NP *the wrong piece* is the complement

of the verb *performed*; while (2.21b) is ungrammatical as the NP *the wrong way* is an Adv.

- (2.20) a. Mary *performed* the wrong piece.
b. The wrong piece *was performed* by Mary.

- (2.21) a. Mary *performed* the wrong way.
b. *The wrong way *was performed* by Mary.
(Radford, 1988:432)

2.2.1.1.1 Constraints on Transitivity

In earlier works on Transformational Grammar, Pass. sentences are formed by selecting the element *Be + -en*. However, this element can be selected, only if the following verb is transitive, e.g. *was + eaten* is permitted; but not *was + occurred* (Chomsky, 1957:42).

However, Chomsky (1965:103-5) observes that there are certain transitive verbs, that do not undergo the Pass. transformation, such as *resemble, have, marry, fit, cost, weigh*, and so on, since they generally do not take Man Adv. freely. For these verbs, the Man Adv. should have as one of its realisations a dummy element, signifying that the Pass. transformation must obligatorily apply. This is represented by the following rules:-

(2.22) Manner \longrightarrow *by passive*

(2.23) NP-Aux. - V... -NP-... - *by passive*-...

The rule has the advantage of being limited to transitive verbs so as to exclude verbs, like *have, resemble*, etc., and to include intransitive verbs that take Man Adv., so that both *John was seen* and *John is looked up to* are formed by the same rule; although only in the former case *John* is the direct Obj. of the deep structure.

Some grammarians, however, argue about the application of the Pass. rule to a list of transitive verbs. Quirk et al. (1985:162) mention that some transitive verbs that are called “Middle Verbs” do not occur in the Pass., such as *hold*, *lack*, *resemble*. Palmer (1974:85), on the other hand, points out that verbs of measurement, such as *owe*, *weigh*, *total*, *cost*, that are followed by NPs indicating quantity, such as *10 dinars*, *1 ton*, *5 KGs*, etc., are intransitive, and therefore, they cannot occur in the Pass. structure. However, when they are transitive, they may be passivised. For instance, *a pound*, and *six inches* are not the Objs. of the verbs; while *the plums*, and *the beans* are, in (2.24), (2.25); and (2.26), and (2.27), respectively.

- (2.24) a. The book *weighs* a pound.
b. *A pound *was weighed* by the book.
- (2.25) a. The boy *grew* six inches.
b. *Six inches *were grown* by the boy.
- (2.26) a. The greengrocer *weighed* the plums.
b. The plums *were weighed* by the greengrocer.
- (2.27) a. The gardener *grew* the beans.
b. The beans *were grown* by the gardener.
(Palmer, 1987:82)

Some linguists argue about the nature of constraints imposed on these verbs. Thus verbs which cannot be made Pass. may be compared with others of very similar meanings which do have Pass. For those, the restriction is certainly not semantic, but syntactic (Gleason, 1965:307; Lakoff, 1970:156ff).

- (2.28) a. Smith *lacks* money.
b. *Money *is lacked* by Smith.
- (2.29) a. Smith *needs* money.
b. Money *is needed* by Smith.

- (2.30) a. Bad luck *befalls* John.
 b. *John *is befallen* by bad luck.

- (2.31) a. Bad luck *struck* him.
 b. He *was struck* by bad luck.

For other linguists, the constraints can be explained in purely semantic terms, by means of Jackendoff's (1972:43-4) Thematic Hierarchy Condition, who states that:-

the passive *by*-phrase must be higher on the thematic hierarchy than the superficial subject.

$$(2.32) \text{ agent} > \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \textit{locative} \\ \textit{source} \\ \textit{goal} \end{array} \right\} > \text{ theme} > \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \textit{NPwhose} \\ \textit{location is} \\ \textit{specified} \\ \textit{Patient} \end{array} \right\}$$

According to this principle, the NP in *by*-phrases must be higher than the Pass. Subj., e.g. agent or experiencer, so as to affect the Pass. Subj. that should be the receiver in this context (Jackendoff, *ibid.*; Chalker, 1984:91; Shibatani, 1985:832).

- (2.33) a. John *loves Mary*. (receiver)
 b. Mary *is loved* by John. (experiencer)

2.2.1.2 Passives of Double Objects

Double Passs. are the constructions that result from the application of NP-Movement to verbs followed by double Obj. NPs, called "ditransitive verbs" (Wasow, 1977:343). The first construction results from the application of the rule to the direct Obj. moving it to the Subj. position. The indirect Obj. that retains in its position is called a "retained indirect Obj". The retained indirect Obj. must be in the *to*-dative case, and the whole

construction is called “direct Obj. Pass.” This is shown in the following example:-

- (2.34) a. The staff *sent* a pork-pie to the general.
b. A pork-pie *was sent* to the general by the staff.

Alternatively, NP-Movement can be applied to constructions which undergo the indirect Obj. shift; whereby the indirect Obj. comes before the direct Obj.; and thus it undergoes the application of the rule. In this case, the direct Obj. completes the predicate and receives the direct action of the verb. Grammarians call this complement of the Pass. verb a “retained direct Obj. complement” (House and Harman, 1950:107; Lapalombara, 1976:51). The resultant Pass. is called “indirect Pass.” However, in the *for*-dative constructions, even when the indirect Obj. that is preceded by *for* undergoes the indirect Obj. shift; and therefore, the indirect Obj. comes before the direct Obj.; neither the indirect Obj. NP nor the direct Obj. NP can undergo passivisation (Huddleston, 1971:97). This explains the grammaticality of (2.35b), and the ungrammaticality of (2.36b and c).

- (2.35) a. The staff *sent* the general a pork-pie.
b. The general *was sent* a pork-pie by the staff.

- (2.36) a. Fred *bought* Ethel a birthday present.
b. *A birthday present *was bought* Ethel by Fred.
c. ?Ethel *was bought* a birthday present by Fred.

In (2.35a.), a *pork-pie* cannot undergo passivisation, as it does not follow the verb *sent* directly. This is based on NP Adjacency Condition which states that only the NP that is immediately adjacent to the VP can be passivised (Radford, 1988:427). The following sentence is, therefore, ungrammatical:-

(2.35) c. *A pork-pie *was sent* the general.²

According to Radford (ibid.:425-6), NP Movement has the effect of preposing only the NP that immediately follows the VP into the preverbal Subj position. In (2.37), the application of NP-Movement to the sentence results in moving *Mary* into the empty NP position to the immediate left of *will*. The derived surface structure, associated with the following sentence, is represented schematically in Figure (2.3) below.

(2.37) a. They *will give* Mary nothing.
 b. Mary *will be given* nothing.

Figure (2.3) NP-Movement in Indirect Passives

Of these two Pass. types, the indirect Pass. is found to be more usual in English. However, the direct Pass. is more usual when it is desired to predicate something about the indirect Obj. (Zandvoort, 1975:56; Quirk et al., 1985:346; Thomson and Martinet, 1986:265).

2.2.1.3 Passives with Predicative Complements

This type is also called “Pass. followed by small clauses”, since the predicative complements are represented by clauses that have the sentence status, not the sentence-bar boundaries status, since they cannot be introduced by complementisers, such as *for*, or *that*, like the majority of other clauses. The predicative complements consist of Obj. NP followed by AP, NP, PP, etc. Hoekstra (1984:203), and Radford (1988:426) consider this type as one of the verbal Pass. types, since it does not have the adjectival status, determined by Wasow’s (1977) four tests for the lexical derivation of the Pass. Besides, NP Movement can operate on the Obj. NP, moving it across the sentence boundaries of the small clause, into the empty Subj. position. This is indicated by the following sentence, and outlined schematically in Figure (2.4).

- (2.38) a. They *found* the prisoner guilty of the charges.
b. The prisoner *was found* guilty of the charges.

Figure (2.4) NP-Movement in
Passives with Predicative Complements

It is worth observing that the AP in the small clause or any other complement to the Obj. NP, cannot undergo NP Movement, since such a complement is viewed as a part of the verb in the deep structure, and it is extraposed to the right of the Obj. NP by a transformation, namely “Object Separation” (Chomsky, 1957:76-7). Therefore, in (2.39a), the complement *boss* is not subject to passivisation as shown in (2.39c); while the Obj. NP that follows that complement is subject to passivisation, as shown in (2.39b), whose deep structure is illustrated in Figure (2.5) below.

- (2.39) a. They *will elect* Harry boss.
 b. Harry *will be elected* boss.
 c. *Boss *will be elected* Harry.

Figure (2.5) The Deep Structure Representing Passivisation of Noun Phrases that Follow Complements Based on Chomsky's (1965) Model

Within the GB³ theory, the application of NP-Movement in Passs. with Predicative Complement is explained in terms of Case Assignment Principle.⁴ By this principle, the NPs that follow Pass. VPs lose their cases, and the VPs assign no roles to their Subj. NPs. Consequently, Case Filter Principle follows, in terms of which the NPs that follow Pass. VPs should receive cases, so as to trigger NP Movement. Thus, the Obj. NP is moved into the Subj. position where it acquires the nominative case (Hoekstra, 1984:197). (see Note 4)

2.2.1.4 Passives Followed by Infinitival Complements with Subjects

Two classes of verbs followed by *to*- infinitive clauses with Subj. can occur in the Pass.: factual and non-factual verbs. These verbs are to be distinguished as taking complex transitive complementation. Factual verbs can be followed by subordinate

clauses that normally have verbs, such as *Be*. Such verbs are, *like feel, find, imagine, know, suppose, think*, etc. For example:

- (2.40) a. John *believed* the stranger to be a policeman.
b. The stranger *was believed* to be a policeman by John.

(Quirk and Greenbaum, 1973:364)

Within the GB theory, and following Radford's (1988) approach, the infinitival complements of predicates, such as *consider, believe*, etc., are also called "exceptional clauses". These clauses are of the frame NP to VP, implying that the NP that is in the Subj. position of the embedded clause is the direct Obj. of the main clause. Therefore, these constructions are also referred to as "accusative Subj. Pass." (Wasow, 1977:343). Radford (1988:426) describes these clauses as having the status of the sentence, not of the S^1 , i.e. the sentence that can be introduced by an overt complementiser. NP-Movement can be applied to the construction moving the Subj. of the embedded clause into the Subj. position of the Pass. construction, as in the sentence (2.41) below, that is represented schematically in (2.42).

- (2.41) a. I *consider* John to be incompetent.
b. John *is considered* to be incompetent.

(2.42) [NP_e] is considered [S John to be incompetent.].

While Radford (ibid.) explains the exceptional behaviour of exceptional clauses in terms of having the sentence status; as they cannot be introduced by overt complementisers, the unusual behaviour of these clauses is attributed to Exceptional Case Marking Principle. By means of this principle, the cognitive or factual verbs

can exceptionally assign the objective case to the Subj. of the embedded clause, and consequently, these verbs can delete the sentence bar of the clauses following them; and change them to possess the sentence status (Cook, 1988:142).

Non-Factual verbs with non-finite constructions express a causative, volitional, or attitudinal relationship with the subordinate clauses. These verbs are like *cause*, *expect*, *hate*, *mean*. The constructions with non-factual verbs are similar to those which have the *to*-infinitive, or the exceptional clauses, with Subj. NPs. Some verbs, however, may take a bare infinitive in their infinitival clause, such as *have* (in the sense of *cause*), *let*, *make*, and some verbs of perception, such as *feel*, *hear*, *notice*, *observe*, *see*, *smell*, *watch*. It is noticeable that in the Pass., the bare infinitives that follow these verbs are replaced by the *to*-infinitives, as in (2.45b), and (2.46b) below. However, this does not apply to *have*, and *let*, that cannot occur in the Pass.

(2.43) They *had/let/made* Bob teach Mary.

(2.44) I *watch* Bob teach Mary.

(2.45) a. I *made* Bob clean his room.

b. Bob *was made* to clean his room.

(2.46) a. I *heard* them shout something.

b. They *were heard* to shout something.

(Quirk and Greenbaum, 1973:365-6).

Constructions containing both factual and non-factual verbs, followed by infinitival complements, can undergo NP-Movement by moving the Subj. NP of the embedded clause across the sentence boundaries, into the Subj. position of the main clause. Thus, the sentence (2.47) is represented in Figure (2.6).

(2.47) a. They *believe* John to be honest.

b. John *is believed* to be honest.

Figure (2.6) NP-Movement in Passives Followed by Infinitival Complements with Subjects

2.2.1.5 Agentive versus Agentless Passives

Agentive Pass. refer to the structures that contain *by*- phrases which can be used as the Subjs. of the corresponding Act. structures. The Pass. structure is agentless if the *by*-phrase is absent, although it is merely understood (or covert). The *by*-phrases can be subdivided into phrases with the agent as animate, or inanimate, as shown in (2.48b), and (2.49b), respectively.

- (2.48) a. John *broke* the window.
 b. The window *was broken* by John.

- (2.49) a. The key *opened* the door.
 b. The door *was opened* with the key.

The NP *the key* in (2.49b) has an instrumental interpretation. Thus, it should be introduced by *with*, rather than *by*, as it presents material; rather than agent (Thomson and Martinet, 1986:267).

Other prepositions, besides *by* and *with*, like *about*, *at*, *to*, can be used in the Pass. structure, introducing phrases which are referred to by Svartvik (1966:196) as “quasi-agent”; and Quirk et al. (1985:169) as “agent-like phrases”. Examples are like the following:-

- (2.50) a. The complication *worried* us.
b. We *were worried* about the complication.

- (2.51) a. Her behaviour *surprised* us a bit.
b. We *were* a bit *surprised* at her behaviour.

It is worth noting that agent phrases are obligatorily attached to some Pass. VPs, such as *follow*, *actuate*, *precede*, *own*, as in:-

- (2.52) a. A short interval *followed* the music.
b. The music *was followed* by a short interval.
c. *The music *was followed*.

- (2.53) a. Both rigorous and political motives *actuated*.
b. The rebels *were actuated* by both rigorous and political motives.
c. *The rebels *were actuated*.

(Emonds, 1976:74)

Agentless Passs., on the other hand, refer to the Pass. structures whose agent-phrases are absent, when the agent is irrelevant, unknown, or redundant; or when the speaker does not want to emphasise it (Crystal, 1997:225), as in the following sentence.

- (2.54) a. People have often *criticised* the prime minister recently.

- b. The prime minister *has often been criticised* recently.

2.2.2 Pseudo-passives⁵

2.2.2.1 Middle Constructions

The relation between transitive and intransitive forms of certain verbs are like the relation between their Act. and Pass. VP forms, in that the Act. Objs. of these transitive verbs can, at the same time, act as the Pass. Subjs., and both the Pass. constructions, and intransitives have the agents unstated. This is represented by the following examples:-

- (2.55) a. John *rang* the bell.
b. The bell *was rung*.

- (2.56) a. John *rang* the bell.
b. The bell *rang*.

The construction that is indicated in (2.56b) is referred to as “the derived intransitive”, as its transitive form seems to be more essential than its derived form. Verbs like these necessitate the participation of the agent; although it is not encoded at all. They express a general tendency rather than a specific event. They do not appear in the imperative, or Prog., and they must appear with Man Adv. (O’Grady, 1980:59-60; Keyser and Roeper, 1984:384-5). Thus, while (2.57a); (2.58a); and (2.59a) are grammatical; (2.58b), (2.59b), (2.60b), and (2.58c), (2.59c), and (2.60c) are not.

- (2.57) a. The clothes *hang* easily.
b. *The clothes *are hanging*.⁶
c. *The clothes, *hang*.

- (2.58) a. Chickens *kill* easily.
b. *Chickens *are killing*.

c. *Chickens, *kill!*

- (2.59) a. Bureaucrats *bribe* easily.
b. *Bureaucrats *are bribing*.
c. *Bureaucrats, *bribe!*

Bakir (1996:42) lists other verbs, such as *bake, fry, convert, build, add, do, cut*, etc., which can have the middle construction interpretation. He gives the following examples:-

- (2.60) a. Lamb usually *cooks* quickly.
b. They *were cooked* in the oven for 45 minutes.

While *lamb* in (2.60a) belongs to things that are quickly cooked, as it has something that facilitates (cooking); (2.61b) answers the question of how the lamb chops were so delicious. O'Grady (1980:66) notes that the derived intransitive constructions are, therefore, used to refer to the contribution that the properties of the Obj. of the verb could make to the actualisation of events. In this example, the derived intransitive makes prominent the properties that the lamb may possess in order to facilitate or hinder the actualisation of (cooking).

As Zandvoort (1962:200) affirms, those verbs are usually used when the Pass. Subj. is non-personal. By contrast, O'Grady (1980:65) argues that the Act. Obj. that is to be used as the Pass. Subj. can be personal, if it is an experiencer, as in the following sentences:-

- (2.61) a. People *read* Shakespeare's plays well.
b. Shakespeare's plays *read* well.

- (2.62) a. People *trust* honest men easily.
b. Honest men *trust* easily.

Although Pass. and middle constructions have different semantic interpretations, as shown in the sentences (2.60a, and b);

syntactically, both have the Obj. NP that originates in postverbal Obj. position, moved into the preverbal Subj. position by NP-Movement.

- (2.63) a. The boy *locks* the door easily.
b. The door *locks* easily.

(2.64) [N_{pe}] *locks* the door easily.

(Radford, 1988:446-7)

2.2.2.2 Prepositional Passives

Prepositional Passs. are the result of applying NP-Movement to the Objs. of prepositions. For instance:-

- (2.65) a. The committee *agreed* upon the proposal.
b. The proposal *was agreed* upon by the committee.

Some Transformationalists account for the transformations involved in the derivation of this construction. Hornstein and Weinberg (1981), as cited in Hoekstra (1984:135), argue that prepositional Pass. is constructed by means of Reanalysis rule, by means of which the whole prepositional VP is rebracketed so as to incorporate the preposition into the verb, leaving the Obj. of preposition to undergo NP-Movement. The process whereby the verb is rebracketed with the preposition is referred to as “Preposition Stranding” (Van Riemsdijk, 1978), as illustrated in Figure (2.7) below.

Figure (2.7) The Reanalysis Rule in Prepositional Passives

Transformationalists differ in positing some restrictions on the application of the Reanalysis rule on prepositional Passs. Chomsky (1965:105ff) finds that the rule cannot apply if the PP following the verb is an Adv. of time, or place; and does not constitute a part of the verb. This justifies the ungrammaticality of (2.66b); and the grammaticality of (2.67b):-

- (2.66) a. They *argued for* many hours.
 b. *Many hours *were argued for* by them.

- (2.67) a. They *argued for* many topics.
 b. Many topics *were argued for* by them.

However, Radford (1988:427) accounts for the restrictions on the Reanalysis rule in constructing the prepositional Passs. in terms of Adjacency Condition. In terms of this condition, the presence of any intervening element or a specifier refrains the Pass. rule from being applied to the VP. Whereas *asked for NP₁*, can have *NP₁* as the Pass. Subj.; *asked NP₁ for NP₂* cannot have *NP₂* as the Pass. Subj.

- (2.68) a. The dean *asked for* the information.
 b. The information *was asked for* by the dean.

- (2.69) a. The dean *asked* the committee for the information.

- b. *The information *was asked* the committee for.

Leech and Svartvik (1975:259), and Quirk et al., (1985:1158) call the prepositional verb in (2.69a) a “ditransitive prepositional verb”.

The Reanalysis rule that is applied to prepositional verbs is only restricted to those VPs that are called “semantic units” (Chomsky, 1977:87; Leech, 1988:333). For Van Riemsdijk (1978:221), this is explained in terms of what he calls ‘possible words’. Thus, *lived in* in (2.70) means *inhabited*, and accordingly can be passivised; while *died in* in (2.71), cannot.

- (2.70) a. Many people *lived in* England.
b. England *was lived in* by many people.

- (2.71) a. Many people *died in* England.
b. *England *was died in* by many people.

Another restriction imposed on prepositional Passs. is in terms of the semantic roles of the Obj. NP following the prepositional verb. For these verbs to undergo passivisation, they must affect the NPs following them. If these NPs have both affected and locative roles, it is usually the affected role that has relevance to the Pass.

- (2.72) a. They *have not lived in* this house for years.
b. This house *has not been lived in* for years.

- (2.73) a. They *have slept in* the village.
b. ?The village *has been slept in*.

- (2.74) a. Small as it was, no fewer than eight monrachs *have slept in* the village.
b. The village, small as it was, *has been slept in* by no fewer than eight monrachs.

(Huddleston, 1971:96, Chalker, 1984:91)

2.2.2.3 Idiom Chunk Passives.

Certain NPs can only occur in conjunction with some specific verbs, and in a position which immediately follows them. These are referred to as “idiom chunk NPs” (Radford, 1988:423).

What is notable about this construction type is the fact that it has two Pass. structures. For example, *take advantage of* in (2.75) can undergo passivisation either by applying NP-Movement to the NP immediately adjacent to the verb *take*, or by applying Reanalysis rule that rebrackets *take advantage of* leaving the NP *someone*, that is adjacent to the verb, so as to match the Adjacency Condition on passivisation, and to undergo NP-Movement. Reanalysis rule that is applied to (2.75) is outlined schematically in (2.76) below.

- (2.75) a. They *take* advantage of someone.
b. Advantage *is taken* of someone.
c. Someone *is taken* advantage of.

- (2.76) a. [v take [NP advantage] [PP of [NP someone]] .
— Reanalysis —>
b. [v take advantage of] [NP someone]. (ibid.:431)

Radford (ibid.:432), however, argues that NP-Movement cannot apply to constructions of the syntactic combination VP NP preposition NP unless this syntactic combination constitutes one semantic unit, a case which explains the ungrammaticality of the following Pass. sentences:-

- (2.77) a. Bill *drinks* brandy after dinner.
b. *Dinner *is drunk* [brandy after] by Bill.

- (2.78) a. None *talked to* Bill about the problem.

b. *The problem *was [talked to Bill about]*
by none.

- (2.79) a. They *read* a book about President de Gaulle.
b. *President de Gaulle *was [read a book about]*.

2.3 The Functions of the Passive

One function of the agentless Pass. is that it allows the agent to be omitted if it is irrelevant or unknown. It can be used when it is felt to be tactless to mention the agent (Freeborn, 1987:119; Fairclough, 1989:125; Greenbaum, 1991:53). For this reason, the Pass. is used when the speaker, or the writer wishes to disassociate himself from bad news; or when he wishes to describe disasters: pain, or loss, where the interest is in the victim and what he has suffered from; than in the precise cause, as in:

(2.80) He *was bitten* by a snake.

(2.81) She *was knocked* down by a car.

(2.82) They *were taken* to hospital.

(Higgins, 1969:71)

Nash (1986:28) believes that one of the uses of the agentive Pass. is to adjust the informational focus. In other words, the Pass. is used in order to bring the agent into the new final position, from its former position at the beginning of the sentence (Chafe, 1970:219; 221). In terms of reordering the agent in the Act-Pass. versions, Nash (1986:28) concludes that the Pass. transformation refocuses the sentence. This is illustrated by the following sentences:

- (2.83) a. Jack *fed* the hungry birds.
b. The hungry birds *were fed* by Jack.

In example (2.83a), the Obj. is realised by the noun denoting recipients: *the birds*, on which the sentence is focused. In example (2.83b), the *by*-phrase, *by Jack*, indicates the agent role, and the focus is on the agent *Jack*.

Nash (ibid.) also notes that the Pass. is used in narrative in order to present a tale of events, rather than to focus on personalities. In this case, *by*-phrase is omitted, as in:-

(2.84) The dishes *have been washed*. The children *have been put to bed*, the fire *has been made up*.

Palmer (1987:83) finds that this function is particularly useful in narrative to retain the same Subjs. in successive sentences, or in a sentence with coordinate clauses.

(2.85) John came in and *was immediately welcomed* by the committee.

Nash (1986:87), furthermore, finds that the Pass. can be used to adjust the rhythm and weight of a sentence, e.g. to correct front heaviness.

(2.86) a. A public anxiously mindful of the toll of lives with the Chicago air disaster *raised* objections.

b. Objections *were raised* by a public anxiously mindful of the toll of lives in the Chicago air disaster.

(ibid.)

The Pass. is used as one of the means by which transitions from clause to clause or sentence to sentence may be facilitated, by means of putting the *by*-phrase or the verb into the end position. For instance:-

(2.87) A fire sermon *was preached* by the bishop who later entertained us with a harmonica recital.

In this example, the noun *bishop* is immediately followed by its relative pronoun *who*, which acts as a convenient antecedent base (ibid.).

Besides its use in narrative texts, the Pass. is used to make detached or impersonal statements, particularly in the language of scientific writing. The *by*-phrase is always omitted in this respect. For Huddleston (1971:104), the writer usually uses the Pass. in reporting a series of actions that are carried out by the same person. Therefore, it is irrelevant to state who actually carried them out. For this reason, Crystal (1997:225) observes that agentless Pass. constitutes around 80 percent of the Pass. used in a text. Here are some examples from scientific texts:-

(2.88) . . . The capillary *was fed* from a micrometer actuated syringe and the cell *was designed* so as to permit a rapid response of working electrode to step pulses of the applied potential.

(2.89) Most of the work has used similar techniques of fixation, dehydration and embedding in risen and it *could be argued* that the methods themselves are creating similarities between the two groups.

(2.90) The pores, which range in diameter from 60 to 600 Å, *may be randomly arranged* as in *Mastigocladus laminosus*.

(ibid.:104, 106)

The Pass., furthermore, constitutes a characteristic of sport commentary. In such a case the function of the Pass. structure emerges in that commentators often see a play before they can identify the player. He gives the following example:-

(2.91) His shot *is blocked* by John.

In this sentence, commentators resort to using the Pass. structure as it allows them to delay mentioning the player's name: *John* in this example (Crystal, 1997:387).

Notes to Chapter Two

¹The combination of (M) Perf. Prog. in the formation of Pass. sentences are very rare in English, as it results in complex types that can usually be replaced by the simple form of the Perf. (Lester, 1971:131-2, Quirk et al., 1972:815).

- (2.92) a. Conservatives *have not been winning* seats lately.
b. Seats *have not been being won* by conservatives lately.

For some linguists even the combination of M. and Prog. results in the following ungrammatical sentence:-

- (2.93) a. They *will be repairing* the chair at the moment.
b. The chair *will be being repaired* at the moment.
(Gleason, 1965:388-9; Whitman, 1975:123)

²Trudgill and Hannah (1985:56), and Radford (1988:427) consider the sentence as grammatical as it is used in some dialects of Northern British English, since in these dialects, the Act. sentence with the direct Obj. NP adjacent to the VP is possible, and consequently, the NP can undergo NP-Movement as it matches NP Adjacency Condition.

(2.94) John *gave* the job Mary.

However, in American English, when the indirect Obj. is pronoun, it cannot be moved into the Pass. Subj. position. In this case, the direct Obj. is the Pass Subj. (Zandvoort, 1975:56). By

contrast, when the direct Obj. is pronoun, it cannot be made the Pass. Subj. In this case, the indirect Obj. can not be made the Pass. Subj. too. Both cases are illustrated in (2.95) and (2.96), respectively.

- (2.95) a. They *gave* him the mastership, on condition that he would take up his duties immediately.
b. The mastership *was given* him, on condition that he would take up his duties immediately.

- (2.96) a. John *gave* it Mary.
b. *It *was given* Mary by John.
c. *Mary *was given* it by John.

(Trudgill and Hannah, 1985:56)

³GB describes knowledge of language as an interlocking set of sub-theories consisting of principles and parameters, such as X-bar-syntax, the projection principle, movement between the two levels: deep and surface structures, bounding theory, theta theory, case theory, binding theory, control theory, the phonetic form and the logical form (Cook, 1988:34).

⁴According to Cook (ibid.:143) case theory deals with the assignment of abstract case and its morphological realisations. Case is assigned to all NP slang case assigners. These cases include the following:-

- (1) Nominative is assigned by the Tns. part of inflection in surface structure to the grammatical function subject.
- (2) Accusative is assigned by the verb in surface structure to the grammatical function object.
- (3) Accusative (oblique) is assigned by preposition to the grammatical function object of preposition.
- (4) Genitive is assigned by the structure NP (NP-).

In addition to case filters, by means of which every phonetically realised NP must be assigned abstract case.

⁵Grammarians add another type of Pseudo-pass., represented by pass. without Act. counterparts. For Mihailovic (1967:318), they are pseudo as the meaning of Pass. does not correspond to the Act. counterpart, as in

- (2.97) a. The priest *marries* John to Mary.
b. They *were married* in the church.

Another class incorporates verbs which have no Act. counterparts, as the Pass. stands in alternation with an intransitive or reflexive forms. For example:-

(2.98) *History is repeated.*
(= History repeats itself).

According to Quirk et al. (1985:170), these Pass. forms, represented by verbs of notion or completion, such as *stop, escape, lose, vanish, surrender*, etc., and verbs of posture, such as *sit*, and *stand*, have Act. rather than Pass. meanings, as in

(2.99) *I'll soon be finished* with this work.

As for the present work, this type will be excluded as the study is chiefly concerned with investigating Iraqi EFL students' use of the structure of the Pass. VP, and the transformed Obj.

⁶Palmer (1987:92) accepts the Prog. use of middle constructions by citing examples, such as the following:

(2.100) *Oranges are selling* cheaply today.

CHAPTER THREE

DATA COLLECTION

The chapter is an account of the practical work that has been carried out in this study. It outlines the main features of the test: validity, and reliability; testing procedures: the pilot administration, the main administration, and scoring the test; and test description of the various questions employed in this work.

3.1 General Objectives of the Test

Each test has certain objectives for which it has been designed. The five questions, including the Recog. and Prod. item tests, are intended to test the first hypothesis. The Recog. and Prod. item tests, along with the Comp. tests, are designed to measure the second, third, fourth and fifth hypotheses. The objectives of the test are, therefore, intended to investigate the hypotheses of the present study which anticipate that:-

- (1) Errors in the structure of the VP are more frequent than errors in the transformed Obj.
- (2) Errors are fewer in number in the area of the Pass. structure when the subjects are explicitly directed to perform the structure than when they are left for their free discretion about it.
- (3) The subjects' avoidance of the Pass. structure in the Comp. tests is predicted by the difficulty encountered in the Recog. and Prod. item tests (see Schachter, 1974).

(4) Second year students make more errors in the area of the Pass. structure than fourth year students of the years involved in the research do.

(5) Errors committed by using the VP that are attributed to interlingual transfer exceed those related to other strategies.

It is the task of the present test, therefore, to validate or refute these hypotheses.

3.2 Specifications of the Behaviour and Content

Areas to Be Tested

The questions of the test are designed in a specific way that measures the objectives for which they have been designed (Table (3.1)). The test, in the present work, has been designed on the basis of the following points:-

(1) A number of Act. sentences that are to be converted into the Pass. are given in the five questions, i.e. the Recog. and Prod. item tests. The sentences in each question should test any of the two aspects: the transformed Obj., and the VP, at the Recog. and Prod. levels.

(2) The Pass. constructions should be introduced to the subjects without instructing them to use the structure in question, as in the Recog. and Prod. item tests, and the guided written Comps.

(3) The guided written Comps. should be designed in a way so as to elicit the subjects' uses of the Pass. structure, realised by the use of the VP, so as to be compared with their performance on the Recog. and Prod. item tests. The aim is to find out whether there is any relation between their performance on both types of tests, and

accordingly, the reason behind avoiding the use of the structure in Comp. writing can, furthermore, be investigated.

(4) The same test is given to the two grades of students, provided that they are equalised in grade level. That is they are equalised in number, age, achievement, and sex.

Table (3.1) Specific Objectives Derived from the Behaviour and Content Areas to Be Tested

Behaviours	Subject Matter	
	Verb Form	The Transformed Obj.
Recognition	1	3
Production	2	4

3.3 Test Description

The test consists of eight questions that are designed to measure the college students' Recog. and Prod. of the English Pass. structure. The first five questions incorporate Recog. and Prod. item tests; while the remaining three questions comprise the Comp. tests. More specifically, the first question is designed to elicit the subjects' responses to the VP at the Prod. level. The second question, along with the fourth one, are designed so that each can measure the subjects' performance on the transformed Obj., and the VP form, at the Prod. level. However, the third and fifth questions are concerned with measuring their performance on the VP form, and the transformed Obj., respectively, at the Recog. level. The majority of the test items were taken from grammar books,¹ and some were constructed

by the researcher and validated by the jury of experts (see 3.4, for validity).

The first question is of the infinitive verb transformation test type (Appendix 3), consisting of ten items that measure the subjects' productive knowledge of VP, Aux. *Be* and past participle, occurring in contexts that equally express the present and past Tns. within the items of the question. However, the items are framed in such a way that only one voice is suitable to yield grammatical and meaningful sentences. The test items are designed in this way so as to test the subjects' ability to identify the contexts that require the Pass. structures, and middle constructions, when they are inexplicitly directed to use the structure, by means of constraining them to use it in the given contexts. It is worth observing, however, that the test items in the question do not purport to investigate the subjects' proper use of Tns. within the given contexts (see limits 1.5).

In Question Two, the subjects are presented with twenty items in the form of questions, with answers represented by words given in a scrambled way, in order to reduce any effort or time exerted by the subjects to produce grammatical and meaningful sentences. The subjects are also required to arrange the words, adding at the same time certain NPs, pronouns, and changing the VP forms. The twenty items are constructed in a way that each pair represent one type of the construction under study. Each two items in any pair occur in the simple present and past Tns., being distributed equally throughout the items of the question.

The researcher assures that each item included in the short-response question can be answered by using another structure, e.g. the Act., Pass., or nominal structures. This is done intentionally in order to achieve the major aim of designing the question, i.e. to make

sure that the subjects are able to identify the contexts that require the Pass. structure after they choose to perform the structure, among the other two alternatives. Besides, the question is intended to measure the productive knowledge of the subjects of the transformed Obj. and the VP. Both aims are achieved without explicitly directing them to use the structure. The preference of using one type to the other one could be investigated in terms of avoiding or using it due to linguistic or non-linguistic factors. The Obj.s. are presented against each item so that the subjects can easily apply the syntactic rule of NP-Movement.

Question Four is, however, concerned with measuring the subjects' Prod. of the transformed Obj. and the VP, when the subjects are explicitly directed to produce the Pass. structure, i.e. the contexts that require the use of the Pass. structure have already been identified by directing the subjects to produce it. This is done by presenting the subjects with ten items in the Act. structure, and the subjects are required to change them into the Pass., leaving them to determine the Pass. VP form vs. the Act. VP form, by adding the sentence *if possible* (Appendix 3).

Question Three aims at measuring the subjects' receptive knowledge of the correct form of the Pass. VP used in the Pass. construction types, or the Act. VP form of middle constructions used in the middle constructions. Ten items make up the multiple-choice question with four distractors among which the subjects are required to make only one correct choice. Each one of these distractors is intended to serve a subtype of errors investigated in the categorisation of errors. The distractors include the Act. simple present Tns., the Act. simple past Tns., the Act. Prog., and the past participle with the Aux *Be* omitted.

The fifth question is meant to find out the subjects' Recog. of the correct application of the NP-Movement rule within the various types under study. The question comprises ten items (five items correct and the remaining ones wrong). The subjects are asked to state whether each item is correct, or not, and correct the wrong ones so that the researcher can ensure that the opportunity of guessing is reduced to the minimum. The five items are written wrongly in order to measure the subjects' ability to recognise the constraints imposed on the application of the NP-Movement rule, so as to render them correct.

As for the Comp. questions, the subjects are presented with three topics and they are instructed to use the information given in each, without being told to use the Pass. structure. The subjects are presented with all the lexical items that they may need in order to reduce their efforts and time to produce grammatical and meaningful sentences.

The first Comp. test aims at investigating the subjects' use of the Pass. in contexts where the emphasis is placed upon the effects of certain events, such as 'the accident'. The subjects are presented with Act. VPs, and NPs that may undergo the syntactic rule of NP-Movement. The topic has carefully been chosen in a way which motivates the subjects to use the Pass.

The second topic is designed to find out the subjects' ability to identify the function of the Pass. in emphasising the processes; rather than the actors or agents involved in these processes, such as 'letter writing', 'stamp posting', etc. Unlike the previous question, the NPs are not isolated from the VPs, so that the effect of identifying the NPs that may undergo the

NP-Movement rule can be realised in the subjects' responses to the Pass.

The third Comp. test aims at investigating the subjects' use of the Pass. in scientific topics, such as 'rubber-making process'. The subjects are presented with the past participle forms in order to trace the effect of presenting these forms on their performance, if they choose to act on the Pass. (Appendix 3).

3.4 Validity

Validity is defined as the extent to which the test measures what it is supposed to measure (Heaton, 1975:153). Face validity is, however, the way the test looks to the examiners, test administrators, educators and the like (Harris, 1969:21).

A sample of the test (Appendix 1) was presented to jurors of experts.² Therefore, a number of sentences were modified or replaced by more adequate ones. Some instructions were modified in order to ensure a full understanding on the part of the subjects while performing the test, e.g. further clues were given with respect to Question Two, in order to make sure that the subjects could confine their time and effort to produce grammatical and meaningful sentences.

As for Comp. tests, the researcher assures their validity by emphasising the fact that the topics were essentially taken from composition and general English language teaching courses (see note 1).

3.5 The Pilot Administration of the Test

The pilot administration of the test refers to 'a tryout of the test to a small but representative group of testees' (Heaton, 1975:158).

A pilot administration was carried out on October 14th, 1998. The item test was given to five subjects from the Department of English, College of Arts, who were seated and were given test sheets. The pilot test helped the researcher to:-

- (1) Tryout the test instructions,
- (2) Check the estimated time required for the subjects to work the items of the test, and
- (3) Discover any weakness in the format of the whole test (Al-Zobaei and Al-Hamadani, 1982:13).

After analysing the subjects' pilot responses to the test (Appendix 1), it has been shown that some modifications were required, involving the instructions of the first, second, and fourth questions, as the subjects made serious inquiries before attempting these questions. Further modifications were made concerning the test items in Question Four in terms of omitting the past participle forms presented against each item, so that the researcher could test their knowledge about both the transformed Obj. and the VP forms. The time required for answering the test items is sixty-ninety minutes (Appendix 3).

3.6 Reliability

Reliability refers to the consistency of scores obtained by the same individuals on different occasions (Lyman, 1973:26-7). There are four methods to estimate test reliability: split-halves, Kuder-Richardson, equivalent forms, and the test-retest method. The latter method is adopted to test the reliability of the Recog., Prod. item tests, and the whole test. This method, as Harris (1969:15) states, refers to the stability of the subjects' scores when the test is given to

them twice with a specified time interval between the two administrations.

In order to carry out the test-retest method, the first test was administered on October 20th, 1998, and the test sheets were administered to twelve subjects (six from the second year, and six from the fourth year), from the Department of English, College of Languages.

After about two weeks, the same test was readministered to the same subjects so as to estimate the reliability of the Recog., Prod. item tests, and the whole test.

Having applied the Pearson formula to the scores of the three groups, obtained from the Recog. and Prod. item tests (Appendix 2), the results indicated that:-

- (1) The Cor. Coef. reliability of the Recog. item tests is 0.60.³
- (2) The Cor. Coef. reliability of the Prod. item tests is 0.899, and
- (3) The Cor. Coef. reliability of the whole test is 0.97.

The results of the pilot test indicates that the reliability of the three groups are very high and stable.

3.7 The Subjects

Second and fourth year students from the Department of English, College of Languages, of the academic year 1998/1999 were chosen to take the test. The choice of the two stages under study was made to test the fourth hypothesis (see 1.3), i.e. to investigate the growth in competence in performing the Pass. structure within two years of study.

Fourth year students were chosen because the students at this year are supposed to have an adequate competence about the Pass. structure, whether they have studied it in grammar books or books of

literature. The choice of the second year students was made on the assumption that the students were supposed to be acquainted with the Pass. structure, being presented in the various books to which they were exposed. Besides, the choice of this year ensures that two academic years are quite enough in order to measure the development in the subjects' performance.

For this reason, ninety-one subjects were randomly chosen from both stages. Non-Iraqis, attendants of any external courses in the TL, those who had spent more than two, or four years at the second, or fourth year, and those who had lived in an English speaking country for more than one year were excluded. Therefore, sixty subjects were sat for taking the test (thirty subjects as a representative sample of each year).

The researcher, furthermore, assured the random choice of the subjects by selecting ten individuals from each section at each year. Moreover, ten subjects were chosen from each section by calling the names of those with the odd numbers, and excluding the others with the even numbers.

As long as the study aims at investigating the growth in competence within two years of study, a cross-sectional analysis has been carried out in the present work. For McLaughlin (1982), it is the study in which a group of learners of different ages are compared at one point in time, so that a great deal of data, if many learners were studied in a short time, can be obtained, and many results can be generalised.

3.8 Scoring Scheme

For a test to be reliable, it must have a consistent scoring scheme. The scoring scheme adopted in this study necessitates that

two possibilities should consistently be followed when scoring the subjects' responses:

- (1) Zero score, if the subject fails to respond to the item; or
- (2) One score, if he recognises the correct VP form in Question Three, or if he recognises the correct/incorrect application of NP-Movement in Question Five. Each item in this question should, however, be scored on the basis of their correction of the wrong item, in order to make sure that the subject could identify the incorrect area, and in order to minimise any possibility of guessing.
- (3) One score, if he produces the Aux *Be*, provided that it should be followed by past participle forms, or if he produces the past participles, provided that it should follow the Aux *Be*.

It is worth mentioning that the subjects' responses were corrected, irrespective of any spelling mistakes committed in producing the past participles. consequently, among the eight forms below, only the last two were considered correct, while the first six forms were wrong and were, thus, scored zero in the present work.

- (1) The window *break*. (X)
- (2) The window *is breaking*. (X)

- (3) The window *is break*. (X)
- (4) The window *broken*. (X)
- (5) The man *is arrived*. (X)
- (6) The chicken *is cooked* easily. (X)
- (7) The window *is broked*. (✓)
- (8) The window *is broken*. (✓)

3.9 The Main Administration of the Test

The test was administered to sixty subjects, from the Department of English, College of Languages (thirty subjects from each stage under study) on November 14th, 1998 (Appendix 3).

In administering the test, the instructions were read, and some clarifications were given with regard to Question Two by giving examples in order to ensure a full understanding of the whole test. The subjects made no serious questions except when they were asked about the meaning of certain words.

One week later, the same group was sat for the second session to take the Comp. test. The subjects were, however, not told to perform the Pass. structure, so that the researcher could investigate their use of the structure in Comp. writing. The subjects were provided with some explanation about the idea of each topic, and were asked to pay attention to grammar; rather than content, so that they could confine their efforts to producing grammatical sentences. They were told to use whatever phrases or clues given in each question.

Most of the subjects attempted all the items in the Recog. and Prod. tests with the time allocated for them, i.e. sixty-ninety minutes. They attempted, however, the three topics of Comp. tests within one hour.

Interestingly, both groups were highly cooperative and were interested in the whole matter.

3.10 Statistical Means

The following statistical method was used:-

The “Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Formula” is as follows:-

$$r = \frac{N \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{[N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2] [N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

where r represents the reliability

n = the whole number of the test group in the test-retest = 12

X = the scores of the subjects in the first test

Y = the scores of the subjects in the second test (the retest)

$\sum X$ = the sum of scores of the subjects in the first test

$\sum Y$ = the sum of scores of the subjects in the second test (the retest)

(1) For the Recog. Tests:-

$$\begin{aligned} r &= \frac{(12)(1080) - (109)(111)}{\sqrt{[(12)(1161) - (109)^2][(12)(113) - (111)^2]}} \\ &= \frac{12960 - 12099}{\sqrt{[13932 - 11881][13356 - 12321]}} \\ &= \frac{861}{\sqrt{2051(1035)}} = \frac{861}{\sqrt{2122785}} = \frac{861}{1456.978} \\ &= 0.60 \end{aligned}$$

(2) For the Prod. Tests:-

$$\begin{aligned} r &= \frac{N \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{[N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2] [N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}} \\ &= \frac{(12)(9613) - (313)(318)}{\sqrt{[(12)(2575) - (313)^2] [(12)(9950) - (318)^2]}} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{115356 - 99534}{\sqrt{[114900 - 97969][119400 - 101124]}}$$

$$= \frac{15822}{\sqrt{(16931)(18276)}}$$

$$= \frac{15822}{\sqrt{3.09430}}$$

$$= 0.899$$

$$= \frac{15822}{17590.649}$$

(3) For the Whole Test:-

$$r = \frac{N \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{[N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2][N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

$$= \frac{(12)(17113) - (422)(429)}{\sqrt{[(12)(169110) - (422)^2][(12)(17425) - (429)^2]}}$$

$$= \frac{205356 - 181038}{\sqrt{[202920 - 178084][209100 - 184041]}}$$

$$= \frac{\sqrt{(57830)(52020)}}{57318}$$

$$= \frac{24318}{\sqrt{6.2236508}}$$

$$= \frac{24318}{24947.25}$$

$$= 0.97$$

Notes to Chapter Three

¹The test items were extracted from Close (1974), and Ward (1966), with some modifications.

The researcher depended on some textbooks for teaching English as a second/foreign language in designing the item tests. These are:-

- (a) Allen, E.D. and R. M. Valette (1972), p. 146.
- (b) Low, O. (1975), p. 34.
- (c) Murphy, R. (1985), p. 87.

With respect to Comp. tests, the three topics were respectively depicted from the following books:-

- (a) Carroll and Hall (1985), pp. 36 and 39.
- (b) Pincas et al. (1982), p. 92.
- (c) Eastwood and Mackin (1989), p. 77.

²The jury members are:-

- (a) The late Prof. Khalil I. Al-Hamash (Ph.D.) College of Education – Ibn Rushd
- (b) Prof. Sabah S. Al-Rawi (Ph.D.) College of Languages
- (c) Asst. Prof. Abdul Latif al-Jumaily (Ph.D.) College of Arts
- (d) Asst. Prof. Adnan J. Al-Jubouri (Ph.D.) College of Education – Ibn Rushd
- (e) Asst. Prof. Fayid R. Rabah (Ph.D.) College of Arts
- (f) Asst. Prof. Firas Awad Ma'rouf (M.A.) College of Education – Ibn Rushd
- (g) Asst. Prof. Kamil Al-Kubaisy (Ph.D.) College of Education – Ibn Rushd
- (h) Asst. Prof. Shaima' Al-Bakri (Ph.D.) College of Education – Ibn Rushd
- (i) Asst. Prof. Lamia' A. Al-Ani (M.A.) College of Education – Ibn Rushd

³For Harris (1969:16-7), the satisfactory reliability Coef. is that which falls between 1.00, which indicates perfect reliability; and zero denoting complete absence of reliability. Milton et al. (1986:395), on the other hand, state that Cor. Coef. reliability of 0.60 is an indication of a strong linear relationship in social sciences.

The researcher could conclude that there are certain factors that may affect the amount of reliability, such as the number of the subjects, and the number of the test items in the Recog. tests (Appendix 3). According to Heaton (1975:155), 'the larger the sample, i.e. the more tasks the testee has to perform, the greater the probability that the test as a whole is reliable'.

CHAPTER FOUR

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The study aims at investigating Iraqi EFL students' use of the Pass. structure in English. It, further, purports to answer the following questions:-

(1) Whether Iraqi EFL students encounter difficulty in the area of the Pass. structure, or not? Which aspect of the Pass. structure is the easiest to learn, and which one is the most difficult among the different variables, i.e. transformed Obj. and VP in the various questions at both the Recog. and Prod. levels?

(2) Has the Arabic language any influence on learning the Pass. structure by Iraqi EFL students?

(3) Does explicitness, in the course of using the Pass. structure, i.e. making students aware of the structure in certain guided exercises, such as transformation exercises, affect their performance to the extent that it differs from that when they are left to their free discretion about the structure, as in completion tests, short-response questions, multiple-choice tests and guided written Comps.?

Could this place the responsibility upon textbook writers and syllabus designers for presenting certain exercises which lead into undesired results? What are the alternatives, if any, that may lead to better results of teaching the Pass. structure?

(4) Is avoidance in using the Pass. structure in guided written Comps. correlated positively with the difficulty that is actualised in the Recog. and Prod. item tests? Are there any other factors that affect Iraqi EFL students' use of the structure?

(5) Do Iraqi EFL students identify the registers in which the Pass. structure is a prominent attribute? Does the responsibility fall,

again, on syllabus designers, textbook writers and teachers in not training students to be familiar with the actual use of the Pass?

(6) Whether Iraqi EFL students progress beyond their level in performing the Pass. constructions under study, or not? In other words, do graders at the early years rank lower than their competents, at the advanced years at the university level?

(a) Whether there is any development felt in the students' performance on the structure in the guided written Comps?

(b) Does the number of the Pass. structure instances rise on, moving up from one stage into another at the university level?

(c) Does the development follow from earlier exposure to the structure in a relatively short period before the students have been tested?

(d) Does this enhance the role of teaching materials and teachers for the effective methods of presenting the structure at the advanced years of study; and, inversely, condemn their role in not introducing the structure at the early years at the university level?

For the purpose of providing answers to the questions mentioned above, the subjects' responses should be analysed in such a way that the analysis of their performance in some questions should be intermingled with theirs in other questions, so as to measure the amount of their receptive and productive knowledge on the variables, namely the transformed Obj. versus the VP, on the one hand; and the main objectives of the test, on the other hand. Both correct and incorrect responses are to be corrected in terms of mathematical percentages. Results are to be provided in order to arrive at the validation or refutation of the hypotheses under study.

Accuracy in the results in the course of analysing errors are to be maintained on the basis of manipulating certain statistical measurements, namely Z-test, ANOVA, Cor. Coef. reliability, and t-test.

4.1 Analysis of Variance

In order to test the effect of groups or categories on a single variable, analysis of variance (ANOVA) of two-way classification is used (Ferguson, 1966:300-25). This method consists of two general steps. The first one investigates whether, or not, the variable measured has a significant effect on the responses of the subjects tested. If the difference between the subjects' responses of certain groups is significant, i.e. the calculated F-value exceeds the tabled F-value at a certain level of significance, the next step, i.e., Scheffé procedure, is followed to calculate the variance between the groups. Hence, this procedure arranges the groups according to their effectiveness, clarifying any significant difference between them.

Accordingly, the results of ANOVA are summarised in Table (4.1). Scheffé procedure is applied, since the F-value, with respect to the subjects' responses, exceeds the tabled value at the level of significance 0.05.

4.2 Discussion of Results

The following interpretation and discussion are based on the statistical findings arrived at after applying ANOVA (Table (4.1)). The other statistical procedures, i.e. Z-test, Cor. Coef. reliability, and t-test, are incorporated within the discussion below.

4.2.1 Transformed Object versus Verb Phrase

From Table (4.1), point (1), it appears that the VP is more difficult than the transformed Obj. in both groups, since the former, i.e., the VP, elicits less correct responses than the latter. The hierarchy proves that the variables affect the subjects' responses as the calculated F-value exceeds the tabled F-value 2.45 at a certain level of significance. This result is arrived at if the subjects' performance at the Recog. level is taken apart from theirs at the Prod. level. Hence, Hypothesis (1) is validated.

With respect to G_2 , however, producing the VP is felt to be less difficult than producing transform in terms of the application of NP-Movement to the various construction types under study, when the subjects are explicitly directed to produce the Pass. structure. Two possible reasons might account for this. First, the students at the advanced years at the university level, i.e. fourth year students, get more exposure to the Pass. VP, through grammar textbooks, or books of literature (poetry, the novel, criticism). Second, the subjects at this year encounter much more difficulty in producing the transformed Obj. than in producing the VP, since they are not acquainted with these constructions, that have been presented in the syllabus without any significant details.

The subjects' failure to produce transform might be attributed to the inaccurate presentation of teaching items (Selinker, 1972:39). The subjects are always presented with the fact that the Pass. structure is constructed by means of moving the Obj. NP that follows the verb to the Subj. position, when practising the rule in transformation exercises.

It is worth mentioning that the same statistical findings that have been arrived at above can be captured on the basis of mathematical percentages (Table (4.2)).

As for the subjects' performance on the variables at the Recog. level, the differences between the subjects' responses are not proved to be statistically significant, in that after applying Z-test, at the level of significance 0.05, it is found that the calculated Z-values in both groups do not exceed the tabled Z-value which amounts to 1.645. The following statistical steps are involved in applying Z-test formula:-

$$Z = \frac{\Sigma d}{\sqrt{\frac{n \Sigma d^2 - (\Sigma d)^2}{n-1}}}$$

Σ = the sum of

$n-1$ = degree of freedom

d = the difference between any pair of observations

Σd = $\Sigma X_1 - \Sigma X_2$

$$Z_{G_1} = \frac{11}{\sqrt{\frac{30(241) - (11)^2}{29}}}$$

$$= 0.7 < Z_{0.05} \text{ not significant}$$

$$Z_{G_2} = \frac{50}{\sqrt{\frac{30(138) - (4)^2}{4}}}$$

$$= 0.34 < Z \text{ not significant}$$

However, a much deeper consideration is needed to investigate the routes of development of the subjects under study while performing the Pass. construction types under study, in the domain of the transformed Obj., and the Pass. VP, at both levels. The aim is to measure the extent to which Iraqi EFL students are aware of the constraints imposed on the application of the Pass. rule.

Based on the findings above, Hypothesis (1) is validated, and it would be better restated as follows:-

Iraqi EFL students encounter difficulties in the area of transformed Obj. and the VP. However, the difficulty encountered in recognising and producing the VP is much more than that of recognising and producing the transformed Obj. However, the students at the advanced stages encounter much more difficulty in producing the transformed Obj. than in producing the VP when they are explicitly directed to perform the Pass. structure.

4.2.2 The Recognition versus Production Levels

As shown in Table (4.1), points (2i and ii), the hierarchy that arranges the variance of the subjects' performance on the variables, the transformed Obj. and the VP, proves that the differences between the subjects' responses are statistically significant in that the calculated F-values exceed the tabled F-values, 3.15, and 2.7, for the transformed Obj. and the VP, respectively. Furthermore, each variable affects the subjects' responses at both the Recog. and Prod. levels. However, the variance of the responses of the subjects in G_2 to the VP at the Recog. and Prod. levels is not statistically significant, i.e. the variable VP at the Recog. and Prod. levels cannot affect the performance of the subjects in G_2 , as shown in Table (4.1), point

(2ii). It is, therefore, concluded that recognising the transformed Obj. and the VP is more difficult than producing them in G_1 , when the subjects are explicitly directed to use the structure. However, the subjects in question encounter much more difficulty in the area of the VP at the Prod. level than on the Recog. level, when they are inexplicitly directed to produce the Pass. structure.

In both groups, the subjects' relatively better performance at the Prod. level, if compared with theirs at the Recog. level, can be justified in terms of Krashen's Monitor Model of language acquisition. That is an L_2 learner has two means of internalising L_2 knowledge. The former is concerned with the formal accuracy of language, i.e. forming a learned system by which a learner is able to check the grammatical accuracy of his utterances (Krashen, 1978:175ff). The latter is devoted to the acquisition of the language. When the learner produces the structure, especially in writing, he focuses on accuracy, rather than fluency. He is bound to make use of the monitor as he has enough time to check his responses with the internalised system stored in the brain. This is so especially in cases where the language has been learnt formally; not naturally, as in the case with our subjects. This leads to the desired result, in terms of which the subjects' responses tend to be more accurate, at the Prod. level.

The subjects' higher rate of correct responses to recognising than theirs of producing the Pass. VP form, when they are not explicitly directed to produce it, can be justified in terms of explicitness, where the subjects at the Prod. level are required to produce the Pass. structure, after they identify the context where the Pass. VP is used, and recognise its form. Students are, therefore

unable to actualise their receptive knowledge about the Pass. structure.

However, the subjects' performance at the Prod. level when they are explicitly directed to use the form, which is better than theirs at the Recog. level, is attributed to the fact that at the Prod. level, they have to produce the form; while at the Recog. level, they have to recognise the Pass. VP form, and identify the context where it is used. The hypothesis should, therefore, be rewritten as:

Iraqi EFL students encounter difficulties in recognising and producing the Pass. structure. The difficulty is felt to be much more at the Recog. level than that at the Prod. level with respect to both the transformed Obj. and the VP. Concerning the VP, however, the subjects encounter much more difficulty in producing the VP than in recognising it when they are inexplicitly directed to use the Pass. structure.

4.2.3 Explicitness versus Subjects' Performance on the Verb Phrase in the Recognition and Production Item Tests and Composition Tests

Table (4.1), points (1), and (3), shows that there is a significant difference in the subjects' performance at the Prod. item tests, and the Comp tests, respectively (except with reference to G₂, see below), which is positively correlated with the amount of explicitness of the Pass. structure that is manifested by each test. In other words, explicitness has a significant effect on the subjects' responses to the Prod. item tests, and guided written Comp. tests. Hence, Hypothesis (2) is validated.

The variation in the frequency of correct responses which is proportioned to the amount of explicitness of the Pass. structure can

also be justified by Krashen's (1978:175ff) Monitor Model. In that the student can check the responses with the monitor by means of the knowledge stored in his brain, especially if the information has previously been learnt in formal situations, as in the case with the Pass. structure having been taught by means of drills and exercises, such as transformation tests. Students get familiar with this type of exercises, as in Question Four (Appendix 3); but not with Question One, or Question Two, or Comp. tests, where students are completely left to identify the contexts that require the use of the Pass. structure, recognise the form, and then, produce it. This is manifested by the results arrived at in the hierarchy where the subjects' correct responses to Question Four exceed those of Question One and Question Two. However, the subjects' correct responses to Question Two exceed those of Question One, where the subjects can identify the contexts that require the use of the Pass., at the moment they choose to perform the Pass. structure.

Concerning the subjects' performance on the guided written Comps., the same result can be maintained by counting the subjects' correct responses to the Pass. VP in relation to the total number of the Pass. structure used in each Comp., (both correct and incorrect), since the correct responses of the subjects in G₂ to Comp. 3 exceed those to Comp. 1 due to the fact that the past participle forms are presented in Comp. 3 (Appendix 3), but not in Comp. 1. This confirms the high rate of errors committed in using the past participle forms wrongly. The subjects' correct responses to Comp. 2 are, however, the lowest among other Comp. tests in both groups, since the subjects in this Comp. have the full decision to produce the structure, without giving them any indication about the Obj. NP to be moved into the Subj. position, or the VP that has to undergo passivisation. However, the

differences between the responses of the subjects in G_2 to the three Comps. are proved to be not significant, in that the calculated F-value does not exceed the tabled F-value 3.15, and accordingly Scheffé procedure cannot arrange these difficulties in a hierarchy (Table (4.1), point (3)).

The results arrived at in Table (4.1), point (4), with respect of the subjects' responses to the Prod. item tests and Comp. tests, which are correlated with the amount of explicitness manifested by each test, can, further, be confirmed by applying ANOVA to the subjects' responses to the whole test, including the Recog. item tests, which proves to create significant differences on it, in that the calculated F-value exceed the tabled F-value 2.265 at a certain level of significance.

It is worth mentioning, however, that the performance of the subjects in G_1 on Comp. 1 is better than that in Comp. 3, since the subjects in question are not completely familiar with producing the Pass. structure by inserting the Aux. *Be* (see errors in omitting the Aux. *Be*).

Context of learning (Brown, 1987:179-80) could be responsible for the subjects' inability to identify the contexts where the Pass. structure is properly used in Question One, and Question Two; and in Comp. tests. The subjects get accustomed to the mechanical change of the Act. into the Pass., through the overuse of transformation exercises, as in Question Four, to the extent that they could not identify the contexts, if they were left to produce the structure without instructing them to do so, as in Question One (Appendix 3).

The hierarchies illustrated in Table (4.1), points (3), and (4), are perfect indicators of the fact that explicitness is moving upwards

and downwards a continuum of difficulty in that the more explicit the structure is to the students, the better their performance is at both the Recog. and Prod. levels (Hypothesis (2)).

The conclusions that are drawn from the statistical findings in (4.2.1-3) can be arrived at by investigating the mathematical percentages of the correct responses to the Recog. and Prod. item tests, as illustrated in Table (4.2) below.

4.2.4 Uses of the Passive Structure in Composition Tests

In the light of the statistical results cited in Table (4.1), point (5), by means of applying ANOVA, which proves that there is statistically significant differences between the subjects' uses of the Pass. structure elicited by each Comp. topic, (since the calculated F-value exceeds the tabled F-value 3.15 at a certain level of significance), it can be concluded that the frequency of using the Pass. structure in comp. 3 is higher than in Comp. 1, and the frequency of using the Pass. structure in Comp. 1 is higher than that in Comp. 2. This is based on counting the ratio of the Pass. VP instances, (both correct and incorrect Pass. VPs), per words as it is used in each essay by the subjects in both groups.

The high rate of the subjects' uses of the Pass. structure in Comp. 3 in both groups can be justified in terms of the following factors:-

(1) The subjects are presented with the past participle forms. This confirms the fact that the subjects encounter difficulties in producing the past participle forms due to the misuse of the Aux. *Be*, or the past participle.

(2) The subjects might be aware of the fact that the Pass. structure is an attribute of the impersonal language, so that they use the Pass. to describe the ‘rubber-making process’.

(3) The subjects might use the Pass. structure as the doer of these processes is completely ambiguous for them.

The instances of the Pass. VP in Comp. 1 are less than those in Comp. 3 due to the following reasons:-

(1) The subjects might be aware of the fact that the Pass. is used when the doer is ambiguous, unknown, or irrelevant. Some subjects, therefore, use the Pass. structure in this context, i.e. ‘the accident’, as the doer is unknown to them.

(2) The subjects could realise the fact that the Pass. structure is used in order to place emphasis on events, processes, and actions, rather than the doers of the actions. They prefer to emphasise the breakage of Aisha’s leg, and the damage of her bicycle, i.e. the result of the accident, rather than the driver, or the accident, i.e. the cause of the accident.

The relatively lower number of the Pass. structure instances is indicated in Comp. 2. This can be attributed to the following factors:-

(1) The subjects are incompetent in realising the fact that the Pass. structure is used to describe processes where the emphasis is placed on receivers, not doers.

(2) Some subjects use the Act., instead of the Pass. structure, in spite of their awareness of the fact that the Pass. structure is an attribute of the impersonal language of science. This is based on the grand number of the Pass. VP used in Comp. 3, (see above in this section).

However, the subjects are, at the same time, aware of their limited productive knowledge of the use of the Pass. structure. Therefore, they choose to avoid its use (see Schachter, 1974). This conclusion is confirmed by the hierarchies listed in Table (4.1), points (3), and (4), where performing the Pass. in Comp. 2 constitutes the most difficult task; and in favour of the small number of the Pass. VP instances used in this Comp. (Table (4.1), point (5)).

The statistical findings cited above lead to the claim that Iraqi EFL students might be aware of using the Pass., in the scientific language; however, they resort to using the Act., as they are, at the same time, aware of their limited productive knowledge about the structure (see section 4.4.3, on avoidance).

Below are some examples which have been extracted from the data to illustrate the use of the Pass. structure in the three Comps:-

Uses of the Pass. in Comp. 1

- (4.1) . . . Because of this terrible accident, Aisha *was injured* in her leg and the accident damaged her bicycle too . . . S8, G₂, Comp. 1
- (4.2) . . . *She *rided* the past road and in the main road there is no traffic and isha was driving in a hurry . . . and the bus couldn't control so the accident *was fall*, The bus hit isha and injured her, and broke her left leg and damaged the bicycle . . . S5, G₂, Comp. 1
- (4.3) . . . The streets *were so crowded* but she did not pay attention of this and she did not look arround her when she passed the street and because of that a bus in a hurry hit her and broke her bicycle . . . S26, G₁, Comp. 1

Uses of the Pass. in Comp. 2

- (4.4) . . . When the letter *is carried* to the post office there the officer has to postmark the stamps on the letters then he sorts the

letters into different towns, he loads the mail into the train, he unloads the mail bags after journey, the postman takes the bags to the post office . . . S20, G₂, Comp. 2

Uses of the Pass. in Comp. 3

(4.5) . . . After the raw-rubber *was dried* with smoke to make it into powder after that . . . the worker vulcanised the raw-rubber with sulphur to make it elastic on the end the raw rubber *was treated* chemicals to prepare it for vulcanisation. S10, G₁, Comp. 3

(4.6) . . . After that it *is cleaned* to remove impurities, then we treated it with chemicals to prepare it for vulcanisation, and lastly we vulcanised it with sulphur to make it elastic . . . S2, G₁, Comp. 3

(4.7) . . . Again we remove the impurities by cleaning it after this they *are treated* with chemicals to prepare it for vulcanisation. S7, G₂, Comp. 3

4.3 Categorisation of Errors

Errors are classified into (1) linguistic types, in terms of linguistic categories, such as omission, addition, substitution, and ordering; and (2) psychological types, which explain the sources of errors, such as interlingual, intralingual, etc. (Taylor, 1976:190-4, Ellis, 1986:52-4).

As for the present work, only the first two categories will be taken into account by analysing the types of errors, namely errors of omission, and those of addition. This will be done by means of classifying errors in terms of (1) omitting both the Aux. *Be* and (*-en*) morpheme, (errors in using the Act. instead of the Pass.); (2) omitting either the Aux. *Be* that is followed by the past participle; or (*-en*) morpheme that is attached to the main verb that follows the Pass. Aux.; and (3) adding the Aux. *Be* and *-en* morpheme, (errors in using the Pass. instead of the Act.)

Corder (1972:36-7) proposes a more adequate classification which is more abstract and systematic, by means of which errors are classified into systems, such as tense, number, mood, gender, and case. This goes in line with the three categories mentioned above, based on Al-Jaff's (1995:124) definition of the wrong use of the Pass. which includes the following cases: "the active form is often used to stand for the passive construction. But even when the passive construction is used either verb 'to be' is missing or the past participle is wrong".

4.3.1 Errors in Using the Active Instead of the Passive

As predicted by Mukattash (1985), who states that Arab students generally tend to use the Act. constructions in place of the Pass. ones, and illustrated in Table (4.3) below, errors in using the

Act. instead of the Pass. constitute the major type of errors in the data in all questions, making up 90.40% in Question One; 39.8% in Question Two; 83.22% in Question Three; 59.09% in Question Four; 72.09% in Comp. 1; 69.23% in Comp. 2; 100% in Comp. 3, in G_1 ; and 78.09% in Question One, 35.3% in Question Two; 74.50% in Question Three; 23.91% in Question Four; 66.6% in Comp. 1; 37.5% in Comp. 2, 96% in Comp. 3, in G_2 , of the total number of errors in the area of the Pass. VP in the questions identified.

As indicated in Table (4.4), errors in using the Act. instead of the Pass. consist in using the Act. simple present/past Tns., and Act. present/past Prog.

However, in comparing errors in using the Act. simple present/past Tns. against using the Act. present/past Prog. in the five question, it is found that 80.30% of the total number of errors committed in the question is in the use of the Act. simple present/past Tns., versus 10.10% in the use of Act. present/past Prog. in Question One; 31.48% versus 8.33% in Question Two; 59.35% versus 23.87% in Question Three; 52.27% versus 6.818% in Question Four; 70.93% versus 1.162% in Comp. 1, 23.07% versus 46.15% in Comp. 2, 97.29% versus 2.702% in Comp. 3 in G₁; while 65.7% of the errors in using the Act. simple present/past Tns. versus 12.38% of the errors in using the Act. present/past Prog. of the total number of errors committed in Question One, 34.14% versus 1.2% in Question Two; 61.7% versus 12.74% in Question Three, 21.73% versus 2.173% in Question Four; 62.96% versus 3.70% in Comp. 1, 0 versus 37.6% in Comp. 2; 96% versus 0 in Comp. 2, in G₂.

This rate of errors, in using the Act. Prog. constructions, instead of the Pass. ones, might be attributed to the fact that the Act. counterparts of the Prog. constructions are some of the first introduced verbal constructions in the syllabus. In fact, the present Prog. is the first verbal constructions that students learn (Bakir and Lazim, 1985:9). Moreover, the possible reasons for the errors made in using the Act. simple present/past Tns. and Act. present/Past Prog., instead of the Pass. constructions, might be attributed to the so-called simplification strategy. As the Pass. structure in the English language consists of more elements than that in the Arabic language, students tend to reduce the number of elements of the Pass. structure in building up the Pass. structure in their approximative system.

The following are examples from the data under investigation:-

(1) The use of the Act. simple present/past Tns. instead of the Pass.

(4.8) . . . *I thank her very much and left the post office because I know how the letters should *sent* . . . S26, G₁, Comp. 2

(4.9) *It *arranged* to leave for London. S1, G₁, Q2

(4.10) *It *found* that the spelling of the word was misspelled. S10, G₁, Q2

(4.11) *It *said* that Mr. William is about to be an influential gentleman. S10, G₂, Q2

(4.12) *A great account *takes* all his suggestions. S2, S8, G₂, Q2

(4.13) . . . *The process of the raw rubber *divides* into six division[s]. The first one is that we take the raw rubber and . . . S27, G₂, Comp. 3

- (2) The Use of the Act. present/Past Prog.
- (4.14) **I am disappointing* that the council have adopted that policy. S14, G₂, Q2
- (4.15) *The rent *has been paying* in the middle of the month. S17, G₂, Q4
- (4.16) *The word *is finding* misspelled. S23, G₁, Q2
- (4.17) *All his suggestions *are taking of* a great account. S3, G₁, Q2
- (4.18) *John *was choosing* as the spokesman of the group yesterday. S1, G₁, Q4
- (4.19) *The door *was shutting* in my face yesterday. S1, G₁, Q4
- (4.20) . . . *In the post office they put the stamps on the letters with taking care of the country and their stamps. After that they *sorting* the letters into the different towns. The mail *are loading* into the train . . . S12, G₁, Comp. 2
- (4.21) . . . *If you want to know how the raw rubber *is making* you ought to know that the raw rubber is . . . S13, G₁, Comp. 3
- (4.22) . . . *but only after effect a sligh [] headache came and she *was leaving* alone in the room thinking about her left hand and about the English homework . . . S7, G₂, Comp. 1

4.3.2 Errors in the Use of the Auxiliary *Be* and the Past Participle

Errors in the use of the Aux. *Be* and past participle come last in Question One making up 3.03% of the total number of errors committed in the question in G₁, and 0% in G₂, 28.70% in Question Two in G₁, and 9.75% in G₂, 0% in Question Three in G₁, and 0.980% in G₂; 14.7% in Question Four in G₁, and 10.86% in G₂,

15.11% in Comp. 1 in G₁, 11.11% in G₂, 15.38% in Comp. 2 in G₁, 25% in G₂, 0% in Comp. 3 in both G₁ and G₂ (Table (4.5) below).

Table (4.6) provides details of errors in the use of the Aux. *Be* and the past participle in all questions.

Following Richards (1971), as cited in Robinett and Schachter (1983:209-10), this type of errors is further subdivided into:

(1) *be* omitted before verb + stem + *ed* (participle), as in:-

(4.23) *He *born* in England

(4.24) *It *used* in Church during processions.

(4.25) *They *satisfied* with their lot.

(4.26) *He *disgusted*.

(4.27) *He *reminded* of the story.

(2) *-ed* omitted after *be* + past participle stem

(4.28) *The sky *is cover* with clouds.

(4.29) *He *was punish*.

(4.30) *Some trees *are uproot*.

(3) *be* + verb + *ing* for *be* + verb + *-ed*

(4.31) *I *am interesting* in that.

(4.32) *The country *was discovering* by Columbus.

As for the present work, only the first two sub-categories are included in the course of analysing errors in the use of the Aux. *Be* and past participle.

Looking at Table (4.6), it is clear that the greatest number of errors is in omitting *-en* morpheme in all questions, (except for Question Three, where this type of errors is not presented as one of the distractors) (Appendix 3). Errors in omitting *Be* come next. The small number of errors in the use of the Aux. *Be* and past participle, in comparison with the other types of errors made in all questions, reflects the strong tendency on the part of students to associate *Be* with the past participle. Context of learning could also be responsible due to the fact that teaching strategy and syllabus design pay due emphasis on the two elements used in constructing the Pass. structure, namely the Aux. *Be* and past participle. Possible reasons, however, for errors made on this type may be due to simplification strategy (Selinker, 1972:40), where students tend to simplify the Pass. structure in English by means of reducing elements due to the

relatively small number of elements of the Pass. structure in Arabic, constructed merely by means of a change in the internal vowel pattern of the Act. verb (Tawfik, 1976:47-65). (cf. Corder, 1979 below).

As shown in Table (4.5), no errors have been made in the use of the Aux. *Be* and past participle in Question One in G₁, a case which might be due to the subjects' familiarity with the Pass. structure of these lexical verbs. The absence of errors made in Comp. 3, however, where the past participle forms are presented in the question (Appendix 3), confirms the fact that the subjects encounter difficulty in producing the past participle, in that when these forms are presented, no errors are made in constructing the Pass. A conclusion which, furthermore, confirms the fact that the subjects can produce the Aux. *Be*, if they are presented with the past participle forms, i.e. errors in omitting *-en* morpheme are more than those of omitting the Aux. *Be*.

Errors in omitting the Aux. *Be* are presented in the following examples:-

(1) Errors in omitting the Aux. *Be*

(4.33) *He *given* money from his uncle who live in London.

S12, G1, Q2

(4.34) *He *know* by a letter sent to them. S12, G1, Q2

(2) Errors in omitting *-en* morpheme

(4.35) *All what I say to him *was took* as a note of. S6, G2, Q2

(4.36) *It *was think* to be born in London. S12, G2, Q2

(4.37) *The rent *is pay* her by the middle of the month. S6, G1, Q4

(4.38) . . . *Her father and mother were waiting for her, but she didn't come. They *were very worry* about her because she always reached home at 12:30 . . . S21, G2, Comp. 1

- (4.39) . . . *She was in a hurry because she had much homework to do before lunch so she used the main road to arrive quickly. The streets *were very crowd*. . . S23, G2, Comp. 1
- (4.40) . . . *As a result the driver of the bus *was not control* . . . S9, G1, Comp. 1
- (4.41) . . . *and because she was in a hurry and the bus had no control, the bus hit Aisha and she fall from the bicycle which *was damage*. . . S12, G1, Comp. 1
- (4.42) . . . *Antitetanus injection, antiseptic cream and three stiches *are require*. . . S12, G1, Comp. 1
- (4.43) . . . *Her left leg *was break* as well. . . S29, G1, Comp.1
- (4.44) . . . *Then the letter *will be sort* into a different town and then . . . S30, G2, Comp. 2
- (4.45) . . . *if there were bags they *will taking* into the post office. Then the letter *will be sort* into the different streets, and the letters *will be deliver*. . . S3, G2, Comp. 3

4.3.3 Errors in Using the Passive Instead of the Active

According to Richards (1971), as cited in Robinett and Schachter (1983:209-10), errors in using the Pass. instead of the Act. are classified into:-

(1) *be* + verb stem for verb stem

(4.46) *We *are live* in this hut.

(4.47) *The sentence *is occur*.

(4.48) *We *are hope*.

(4.49) *He *is speaks* French.

(4.50) *The telegraph *is remains*.

(4.51) *We *are walk* to school everyday.

(2) *be* + verb stem + *-ed* for verb + stem + *-ed*

(4.52) *Farmers *are went* to their houses.

(4.53) *He *was died* last year.

(4.54) *One day it *was happened*.

(4.55) *They *are opened* the door.

(3) *be* + verb + *-ed* for verb stem

(4.56) *The money *is belonged to*.

(4.57) *The machine *is comed* from French.

For the case of the present research, however, errors in the use of the Pass. instead of the Act. include the following subcategories:-

(1) Adding the Aux. *Be* and *-en* morpheme for Act. verbs; and

(2) Adding the Aux. *Be* and *-en* morpheme for middle verbs, i.e. verbs used in the Act. form to convey Pass. meaning in certain contexts.

Errors in using the Pass. instead of the Act. are the second highest in all questions, in that in Question One it constitutes 6.56% of the total number of errors committed in the question, in Question Two 31.48%; in Question Three 16.77%; in Question Four 26.13%, in Comp. 1 12.79%, in Comp. 2 15.38%; and in Comp. 3 0%, with respect to G₁. However, it constitutes 21.90% of the total number of errors committed in Question One, 24.50% in Question Three, 22.22% in Comp. 1, 37.5% in Comp. 2, 4% in Comp. 3, with respect to G₂, (except for the total percentages of errors made in Question Two and Question Four in G₂, which stand oddly amongst the conclusion arrived at in this paragraph). (Table 4.7).

It is worth noting that errors in using the Pass. instead of the Act., that are attributed to the subjects' failure to produce middle constructions correctly may be due to the fact that the subjects do not distinguish between middle constructions and Pass. constructions. More specifically, they cannot identify the contexts that require the use of either.

The following examples that represent the type in question are from the data under study:-

(1) Errors in using the Pass. instead of middles

(4.58) *Shakespeare's books *are well-read*. S2, G1, Q2

(4.59) *The meat which I bought from this store *was easily cooked*.
S2, G1, Q2

(4.60) *Shakespeare's books *are well read* by people. S6, G2, Q2

(4.61) . . . *At the same time she have passed the road a bus came in a hurry because the driver couldn't control it. The bus and Aisha's bicycle *have been collided*. . . S14, G2, Comp. 1

(2) Errors in using the Pass. instead of the Act.

(4.62) *Noreman *had been landed* on the coast of North America in 10th or 11th century. Those who was the first to discovered.
S7, G1, Q2

(4.63) *John's parents *were known* about his death by sent a letter.
S5, G2, Q2

(4.64) . . . *and finally the material which *is resulted* from this experience [operation, preparation for vulcanisation] is vulcanised with sulpher to make it elastic. S20, G2, Comp. 3

(4.65) . . . *Aisha *was leaving* the school to go to her house by bicycle and she was rodden past the road, but there was no traffic in the main road. . . S7, G2, Comp. 1

(4.66) . . . *The driver *was helped* to stop and he went to the telephone and called the hospital. . . S24, G2, Comp. 1

- (4.67) . . . *Aisha the cyclist had an accident when she *was returned* from the school. She was bicycling from after she left the school and she was thinking if she could. . . S19, G2, Comp. 1
- (4.68) . . . *In the hospital she *was fallen* under a medical check up to make sure that there is no serious inner bleeding or no broken neck. . . S19, G2, Comp. 1
- (4.69) . . . *But one day when she *was finished* her lessons she was in a hurry so as to reach home at lunch time. . . S2, G1, Comp. 1
- (4.70) . . . *The bus in a hurry, therefore the accident *was falled*. . . S10, G1, Comp. 1
- (4.71) . . . *and she felt fear and horrible from what *was happen* to her. She *was drive* slowly, but the road no traffic . . . S28, G1, Comp. 1
- (4.72) . . . *She *was ride* the bicycle in the road. . .
- (4.73) . . . *The accident *was fall* when a driver a very hurry. . .
- (4.74) . . . *and *she feld* in the road . . .
- (4.75) . . . *and the driver *was help* and stop at once . . .
- (4.76) . . . *The doctor *is write* a report.
- (4.77) . . . *The assistant *was carried* to the strecher. . . S28, G1, Comp. 1

4.4 Factors Behind Errors

Explanation of errors consists in explaining how and why errors occur in terms of the possible psycholinguistic sources, so as to determine the cognitive strategies underlying them (Corder, 1971:24). Thus, classifying errors according to their sources necessitates that the strategies underlying them should be investigated first.

According to Brown (1987:177-87), the strategies include:-

(1) Interlingual and intralingual errors which only include overgeneralisation, as the other strategies included in Richards (1971) below, are confined to characterising only the English language as a second/foreign language, and not any other language. Therefore, the latter, i.e., the intralingual errors, is, further, subdivided in Richards (ibid.:199-214) into:-

- (a) overgeneralisation
 - (b) ignorance of rule restrictions
 - (c) incomplete application of rules
 - (d) false concepts hypothesised
- (2) Context of learning
- (3) Communication strategies

Brown (1987:91) considers learning strategies as the input—to processing, storage, and retrieval; while communication strategies are concerned with the output, how to express meaning in language, how we act upon what we already know or presume to know. As they are resorted to when a student tries to get a message across to a student or reader, communication strategies could, therefore, include the process of interlingual, intralingual transfer, and context of learning. They are conscious plans for solving what to an individual presents itself as a problem in reaching a particular goal (Faerch and Kasper, 1983:36).

According to Tarone (1981:286), communication strategies include processes like paraphrase, borrowing, appeal for assistance, mime and avoidance (see Brown, 1987:180-7, for a discussion on communication strategies). In the case of this work, only avoidance is involved among other communication strategies.

4.4.1 Transfer

4.4.1.1 Interlingual Transfer

Transfer refers to the carryover of a previous performance or knowledge on subsequent learning (ibid.:81). Interlingual transfer is the negative influence of mother tongue on learning (Van Els et al., 1984:49).

Errors in using the Act. instead of the Pass., and errors in omitting the Aux. *Be* followed by the past participle, are the two categories for which the transfer effect is very clear, since there are fundamental differences between Arabic and English regarding these two categories. In Colloquial Iraqi Arabic, passivisation is expressed by means of morphological devices,¹ i.e. a change in the internal vowel pattern of the verb, as represented by the Pass. structure of the BA verbs,

/ktal - ?inkital/ (kill - was killed)

/brhan - ?it + barhan/ (prove - was proved)

Tawfik (1976:21-65), therefore, predicted that Iraqi students would commit errors in omitting the Aux. *Be* as they lack this element in their native language.

Bakir and Lazim (1985:18), however, find out that interference, i.e. interlingual transfer, cannot account for errors committed in the area of the Pass. structure, as each language expresses the structure by different means, i.e. English expresses the Pass. structure by both syntactic and morphological means; while in Arabic, the Pass. structure is constructed by morphological means only. Al-Khafaji (1972), furthermore, accounts for the lack of the formal equivalence between the two languages in relation to the Pass. structure. Accordingly, as transfer cannot play a role in uncomparable

structures, the influence of L₁ transfer on TL can only be involved indirectly through the process of simplification (Selinker, 1972).

However, Corder (1979:110) proposes that a student cannot simplify what s/he does not possess. For simplification is the process of uncomplicating, and reducing events to a common dominator to as a few parts of features as possible (Brown, 1980:86). This conclusion can only lead us to accept Tawfik's prediction of the errors made due to interference.

However, if the student produces an utterance *he hitting me*, where the Aux. *Be* is omitted, this can only constitute linguistic simplification if the student is shown to possess an Aux. *Be* in his interlanguage. For Ellis (1986:178-9), this runs up against Corder's (1979) logical objection that the student cannot simplify what s/he does not possess.

Stemming from Tawfik's (1976) and Ellis' (1986) conclusions, it is only natural that the interference that has an influence on the interlanguage of our subjects can only be attributed to linguistic simplification.

Looking at Table (4.4) and Table (4.6), we find that errors in omitting the Aux. *Be* and in using the Act. instead of the Pass. are indicative of interlingual transfer in terms of using the Pass. VP without the Aux. *Be*. One can, furthermore, see that this is the overwhelming strategy employed by our subjects in the area of the Pass VP among other strategies involved in this study. Thus, Hypothesis (5) is validated.

4.4.1.2 Intralingual Transfer (Overgeneralisation)

The term overgeneralisation is defined as a reliance on a prior learning to facilitate new learning, i.e. using the L₁ to understand TL

norms. However, it is a process in which a language learner uses a syntactic rule of the TL inappropriately when he attempts to generate a novel target utterance (Taylor, 1975:74).

Evidence of such a strategy is errors committed by omitting *-en* morpheme and errors in converting the Pass. instead of the Act. (see Table (4.6), and Table (4.7), for errors in the use of the Aux. *Be* and past participle, and errors in using the Pass. instead of the Act., respectively).

Errors which are made by omitting *-en* morpheme could be attributed to the fact that a student uses the Act. form of the verb preceded by the Aux. *Be* due to his/her previous experience about the Act. structure. Accordingly, the deviant structure results in the following sentence:-

(4.78) . . . *and also her bicycle *was damage*. . . S28, G2, Comp. 1

Errors committed by using the Pass. instead of the Act., however, could be attributed to the students overgeneralising the use of the Pass. structure in contexts that require the Act. use of the verbs. In doing so, the students cannot distinguish between the meaning that each voice may convey in a certain context.

4.4.1.3 Ignorance of Rule Restrictions

Errors related to this category are committed due to the students' failure to observe the restrictions of existing structures, i.e. the application of rules to contexts where they do not apply (Richards, 1971:199-203).

This is related to the subjects' performance on middle constructions, where they failed to observe the restrictions under which the Pass. structure could, or could not, apply in a certain

context. Students produced deviant structures as they could not identify the contexts where middle constructions are used, as in the following example:-

(4.79) *People usually buy plays written by Shakespeare because his books *are read* well. S1, G2, Q1

Another instance for which this strategy could be involved is when the student fails to observe the restrictions imposed on the application of the NP-Movement rule in that s/he thinks that the Subj. NP of *that*-clause can undergo NP-Movement, and therefore, it can be moved across S-bar boundaries, resulting in the following deviant sentence:-

(4.80) *Mary *is expect* that he will win. S22, G1, Q4

This category is responsible for the students' failure to observe the syntactic restrictions imposed on the NP-Movement rule. Subject One, for instance, applied the syntactic rule to the NP functioning as an Adv., ignoring the fact that this rule can only apply to NPs that function as complements to VPs.

(4.81) *All afternoon *is played* by few children.

(4.82) *The office *is worked at* by a lot of people. S1, G2, Q5

Further evidence of errors due to ignorance of rule restrictions is the subjects' failure to observe the distribution of the causative verbs in terms of being subcategorised with, or without, *to* when they are made Pass.

(4.83) We *are let to* go. S2, G2, Q4

(4.84) They *were seen go* out. S20, G2, Q5

4.4.2 Context of Learning

Errors related to context of learning follow from the ‘classroom context’, including the teacher or the textbook, or both. Students often make errors because of misleading explanation from the teacher, because of a pattern that was memorised by rote but not properly contextualised (Brown, 1987:179).

In this piece of work, using the Pass. instead of the Act. is the category that best reveals the effect of context of learning. The subjects’ performance on using the Pass. instead of the Act. may be attributed to the overuse of transformation exercises when presenting the Pass. structure in English. Students get used to producing the form of the Pass. VP, without paying attention to the meaning of the Pass. structure.

Another instance is the use of the Pass. VP forms instead of middle constructions, which may be due to the fact that only lip service attention is paid to this construction in grammar books without any significant details about the meaning which differentiates it from the Pass. construction (see Table (4.7), for errors in using the Pass. instead of the Act.).

Richards (1971:203-14) and Ellis (1986:53) propose that students may add the Aux. *Be* because they think of it as a present or past Tns. marker in the following sentences: **One day it was happened*, and **She is speaks French*. It represents the students’ hypothesising false concepts about the TL. This is referred to in Richards (1971:203-14) as false concepts hypothesised.

(4.85) . . . **The bus was in a hurry, therefore the accident was fallen.*
. . S10, G1, Comp. 1

(4.86) . . . **But one day when she was finished her lessons she was in a hurry so as to reach home at lunch time.* . . S1, G1, comp. 1

(4.87) . . . *and she felt fear and horrible from what *was happen* to her.

(4.88) . . . *She *was drive* slowly, but the road no traffic. . . S28, G1, Comp. 1

4.4.3 Avoidance

Avoidance strategy is the skill through which L₁ students avoid L₂ patterns whose experience has shown them to be difficult (Kleinmann, 1977). Levenston (1971) used ‘under representation’ to be confined entirely to the selective avoidance, by means of which L₂ students select to avoid L₂ items which they find difficult, and instead, they are exotic to items from their L₁, or overindulge items that are similar to them.

This matches Schachter’s (1974:361) conclusion:-

if a student finds a particular construction in the [L₂] difficult to comprehend, it is very likely that he will try to avoid producing it.

Accordingly, the difficulty in producing a grammatical concept is linked with the non-use of it, as it is revealed in Comp. tests.

For Kleinmann (1977:365), avoidance must occur without ignorance, in that students must be able to choose not to avoid, and be able to use the form in question. Besides, it cannot be used as a predictor of difficulty, unless it is presupposed by Contrastive Analysis, and proved by Error Analysis. Avoiding a syntactic feature is estimated by psychological, rather than linguistic factors, such as confidence, preference, achievement, success assessment, anxiety, etc.

Among the various types of avoidance strategies, the commonest type is syntactic avoidance, where L₂ students can make

use of paraphrase relation in order to avoid difficult structures, i.e. by rewording the message (Schachter, 1974:361; Hamayan and Tucker, 1979:85; Brown, 1980:166).

The second type is semantic avoidance, which is manifested when there is a lack of vocabulary knowledge, and therefore, they choose a synonym, a superordinate term, or paraphrasing. For instance, students avoid a talk about concepts for which their vocabulary is lacking (Kleinmann, 1977:364).

Topic avoidance, similarly, is identified by students avoiding the talk about concepts. The motivation is their lack of the required structure, i.e. L₂ students avoid talking about what happened yesterday, if the past Tns. is unfamiliar (Brown, 1980:179).

What is relevant to the present work is the syntactic avoidance, whereby the subjects under study are supposed to avoid the syntactic aspect, the Pass. structure, by means of resorting to a simpler structure while still conveying the same meaning, e.g. paraphrasing through producing Act. sentences.

4.4.3.1 Avoidance in Subjects' Performance

Avoidance is one of the strategies that plays an important role in the products of our subjects. It is to be discussed from two perspectives: avoidance of structure in which the whole Pass. structure is avoided, and avoidance of a particular structure of the different types of the Pass. constructions under study.

(1) Avoidance of the Pass. structure

The results of the Comp. tests are compared with those of the Recog. and Prod. item tests, since it is a means of comparing the number of Pass. structures used by a given subject in the Comp. tests with the performance of the same subjects in questions which measure their Recog. and Prod. of the Pass. structure. That is, for any given individual, the researcher could compare the actual difficulty that a person faces with the Pass. structure, with the number used in the Comp. tests. The researcher, therefore, counts the number of the Pass. VPs per essay, dividing them by the number of words in the essay to form a proposition which could be used to compare subjects. The results in (Appendices 4 and 5) represent the number of the Pass. VPs per word used by each individual subject, together with the number of correct responses to the other Recog. and Prod. item tests. If the number of the Pass. VPs used is a true predictor of difficulty, one will expect that the figures of the Comp. tests will positively correlate with actual difficulty in the Comp. tests. The results point to the contrary. The relation between them is not statistically significant. The Cor. Coef. reliability has, therefore, been performed to test the following null hypothesis:-

$H_0: P = O$, versus

$H_{01}: P \neq O$

This has been done by applying the following formula:-

$$r = \frac{n \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} \sqrt{n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2}}$$

The subjects' responses have, furthermore, been subject to t-test, to check whether the results of correlation are statistically significant or not in both groups. T-test formula is as follows:-

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}}$$

As can be seen from the figures in Table (4.8), the relation between the Comp. tests and the Recog. and Prod. item tests is not statistically significant.

Cor. Coef.

Comp. 1

$$G_1Q1 = 0.14$$

$$G_1Q1/a = - 0.01$$

$$G_1Q2 = 0.39 \text{ (significant)}$$

$$G_1Q2/a = 0.24$$

$$G_1Q4 = 0.14$$

$$G_1Q4/a = 0.51 \text{ (significant)}$$

Comp. 2

$$G_1Q1 = - 0.2$$

$$G_1Q1/a = - 0.31$$

$$G_1Q2 = 0.05$$

$$G_1Q2/a = 0.22$$

$$G_1Q4 = - 0.13$$

$$G_1Q4/a = 0.22$$

Comp. 3

$$G_1Q1 = 0.08$$

$$G_1Q1/a = 0.31$$

$$G_1Q2 = 0.05$$

$$G_1Q2/a = 0.06$$

$$G_1Q4 = 0.26$$

$$G_1Q4/a = 0.16$$

Comp. 1

$$G_2Q1 = - 0.02$$

$$G_2Q1/a = 0.23$$

$$G_2Q2 = 0.06$$

$$G_2Q2/a = - 0.09$$

$$G_2Q4 = - 0.04$$

$$G_2Q4/a = 0$$

Comp. 2

$$G_2Q1 = - 0.01$$

$$G_2Q1/a = - 0.09$$

$$G_2Q2 = 0.18$$

$$G_2Q2/a = 0.24$$

$$G_2Q4 = 0.13$$

$$G_2Q4/a = 0$$

Comp. 3

$$G_2Q1 = 0.09$$

$$G_2Q1/a = 0.35$$

$$G_2Q2 = 0.22$$

$$G_2Q2/a = 0.26$$

$$G_2Q4 = 0.09$$

$$G_2Q4/a = 0$$

The figures above show that the correlation between the subjects' performance on the Comp. tests and the Prod. item tests is

not enough, both when the subjects' responses to all Pass. constructions of the Prod. item tests, and when the subjects' responses to one Pass. construction type, namely the Pass. of verbs followed by single NPs, have been calculated. This is so in spite of the relatively high figures of correlation of G_1 , regarding the subjects' responses to the Pass. in Question Two; and the subjects' responses to the Pass. of verbs followed by single NPs in Question Four, which stand oddly amongst the rest. This means that the use of the Pass. VPs is not correlated with the students' awareness of the structure. This finding is consistent with Kleinmann's findings, in which avoidance is also found to be a strategy used by L_2 students though it could not "be attributed to lack of knowledge" of the avoided structure (1977:367). Rather, it could be correlated with affective variables, primarily, confidence in one's ability to deal with a given structure.

This is also true of the results of the correlation between the subjects' performance on the Comp. tests and the Recog. tests. The figures are:-

Comp. 1

$$G_1Q3 = - 0.01$$

$$G_1Q3/a = - 0.011$$

Comp. 2

$$G_1Q3 = - 0.13$$

$$G_1Q3/a = - 0.23$$

Comp. 3

$$G_1Q3 = 0.1$$

$$G_1Q3/a = - 0.08$$

Comp. 1

$$G_2Q3 = 0.24$$

$$G_2Q3/a = 0.07$$

Comp. 2

$$G_2Q3 = 0.13$$

$$G_2Q3/a = 0.12$$

Comp. 3

$$G_2Q3 = - 0.04$$

$$G_2Q3/a = - 0.21$$

The figures above show that the subjects' performance on the Comp. tests does not correlate positively with their performance on the Recog. test.

The results of the correlation of the Recog. test are similar to those of the Prod. item tests in spite of the fact that the Recog. test is a measure of the receptive knowledge of the students; while both the Prod. item tests and Comp. tests measure some aspect of their productive competence. Thus, Kleinmann (1977) indicates that the amount of avoidance which shows up in elicited responses could not be correlated with difficulty, since the subjects can recognise as well as produce the structure. However, they may not use it in their written communication (page 367).

Table (4.8) Coefficient Reliability and Calculated
t-Value of the Recognition and Production Item Tests
and Composition Tests

G ₁ Comp. 1 Q1 = 0.14 t = 0.75 Q1/a = - 0.01 t = - 0.05	Q2 = 0.39 t = 2.24 Q2/a = 0.24 t = 1.31	Q4 = 0.14 t = 0.75 Q4/a = 0.51 t = 3.14	Q3 = - 0.01 t = - 0.05 Q3/a = - 0.11 t = - 0.59
Comp. 2 Q 1 = - 0.2 t = - 1.08 Q1/a = - 0.31 t = -1.73	Q 2 = 0.05 t = 0.26 Q2/a = 0.22 t = 1.19	Q4 = - 0.13 t = - 0.69 Q4/a = 0.22 t = 1.19	Q3 = - 0.13 t = - 0.69 Q3/a = - 0.23 t = -1.25
Comp. 3 Q 1 = 0.08 t = 0.42 Q1/a = 0.31 t = 1.73	Q2 = 0.05 t = 0.26 Q2/a = 0.06 t = 0.32	Q4 = 0.26 t = 1.42 Q4/a = 0.03 t = 0.16	Q3 = 0.1 t = - 0.53 Q3/a = - 0.08 t = - 0.42
G ₂ Comp. 1 Q1 = - 0.02 t = - 0.11 Q1/a = 0.23 t = 1.25	Q2 = 0.06 t = 0.32 Q2/a = - 0.09 t = - 0.48	Q4 = - 0.04 t = - 0.21 Q4/a = 0 t = 0	Q3 = 0.24 t = 1.31 Q3/a = 0.07 t = 1.97
Comp. 2 Q1 = - 0.01 t = - 0.05 Q1/a = - 0.09 t = - 0.48	Q2 = 0.18 t = 1.44 Q2/a = 0.24 t = 1.31	Q4 = 0.13 t = 0.69 Q4/a = 0 t = 0	Q3 = 0.13 t = 0.69 Q3/a = 0.12 t = 0.64
Comp. 3 Q1 = 0.09 t = 0.48 Q1/a = - 0.35 t = -1.98	Q2 = 0.22 t = 1.19 Q2/a = 0.26 t = 1.42	Q4 = 0.09 t = 0.47 Q4/a = 0 t = 0	Q3 = - 0.04 t = - 0.23 Q3/a = - 0.21 t = - 1.14

(2) Avoidance of a particular Pass. structure

It is evident that the Pass. of verbs followed by *that* clause is the most frequently avoided structure, in that, with respect to G₁, out of thirty-five responses to the Pass. construction type, represented by the items 3 and 4 (Appendix 3), instead of any other structure, such as the Act. or nominal structure, thirteen responses, i.e. (37.4%) are drawn to use the Passs. followed by infinitival complements as Subjs., (accusative Subj. Passs.), instead of the Pass. construction in question, i.e. Pass. of verbs followed by *that* clauses. The same conclusion is applicable to G₂. In that out of sixty responses to the Pass. construction type, represented by the same items, 3 and 4 (Appendix 3), forty-nine responses to the Pass. construction type are drawn, and seventeen responses out of the total responses to the item consist in using Passs. followed by infinitival complements as Subjs., i.e. accusative Subj-Pass., i.e. (34.69%), instead of using Pass. of verbs followed by *that* clauses. It is evident from this that avoiding the structure could be attributed to difficulty in producing the empty Subj. *it* (Higgins, 1969:70-4), and accordingly, avoidance is seen as a predictor of difficulty (Schachter, 1974). Moreover, it could be indicative of the effect of some psychological variables, like confidence in the subjects' linguistic knowledge about the Pass. construction type.

From this, it could be concluded that Iraqi EFL students resort to avoidance when they come across the Pass. structure. However, avoidance of the Pass. structure in Comp. tests is not positively correlated with difficulty inherent in the complexity of the English language. Rather, it is affected by some psychological variables, such as confidence in the students' linguistic knowledge

about the Pass. structure. Thus, Hypothesis (3), is refuted in both groups.

4.5 Development in Subjects' Performance

In order to test the development in the subjects' Recog. and Prod. item tests, and Comp. tests, the subjects' correct responses to the Recog., Prod. item tests, and Comp. tests in G_1 and G_2 are compared by means of correlated Z-test. Furthermore, the subjects' uses of the structure are also compared in both groups in order to find out whether the subjects' uses of the structure increase, or not, measured cross-sectionally in G_1 and G_2 .

4.5.1 Subjects' Performance on the Recognition and Production Item Tests

The analysis proceeds in this section to test whether there is significant development in the subjects' performance on the Recog. and Prod. item tests between G_1 and G_2 (two years in between the two groups), or not. The following hypothesis is, therefore, tested:-

Ho : The subjects' scores in G_1 are equal or smaller than their scores in G_2 .

If this hypothesis is validated, it means that there is a significant difference between the scores in G_1 and G_2 , i.e. there is significant development. Z-test formula is, consequently, calculated to the two variables in the Recog. and Prod. item tests in G_1 and G_2 . The figures computed are as follows (Appendix 5, for subjects' performance on the Recog. and Prod. item tests).

G_1 and G_2

the tabled value which amounts to 1.645 at the level of significance 0.05.

The computed figures are as follows:-

G₁ and G₂

Z = 3.02 > Z = (1.645) (significant)
Comp. 1 0.05

Z = 4.44 > Z = (1.645) (significant)
Comp. 2 0.05

Z = 0.84 < Z = (1.645) (not significant)
Comp. 3 0.05

The result is significant at the level of 0.05, which means that there is a significant difference between the scores of each group, in Comp. 1, and Comp. 2. With respect to Comp. 3, however, there is no significant development as the subjects in both groups are presented with the past participle forms which should be utilised in performing the Pass. structure. A conclusion which may lend further support to the fact that the subjects in G₁ encounter difficulty in producing the past participle (see errors in the use of the Aux. *Be* and past participle). It is evident by now, on the basis of the cross-sectional analysis, that there is significant development between both groups in performing the Pass. structure in written Comps., and that Hypothesis (4), with regard to Comps. tests are, therefore, validated.

4.5.3 Uses of the Passive in Composition Tests

The next step is to investigate development through time cross-sectionally in using the Pass. structure instances in Comp. tests. By using the same statistical procedures, the number of Pass. structure instances (correct and incorrect responses) is compared

through groups, so that the following null hypothesis could be investigated.

Ho: The subjects' scores in using the Pass. structure instances in Comp. tests in G₁ are equal or larger than those in G₂.

In order to validate the null hypothesis, Z-test has been conducted, and it has been proved that the calculated Z-value is larger than the tabled value which amounts to 1.645 at level of significance 0.05.

$$Z = \frac{(\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2) - (M_1 - M_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

X₁ = the mean of subjects' scores in G1.

X₂ = the mean of subjects' scores in G2.

S₁ = Standard deviation in G1 S₁² = the variance in G1

S₂ = Standard deviation in G2 S₂² = the variance in G2

n = the total number of the subjects in each group = 30.

The results are as follows:-

Z = - 0.64 (not significant)
Comp. 1

Z = 2.6 (significant)
Comp. 2

Z = - 0.09 (not significant)
Comp. 3

This shows that the difference is significant only with respect to Comp. 2. It is only natural, then, to conclude that there is a significant development in the use of the Pass. structure instances in G_1 and G_2 in Comp. 2, as the subjects in this question are relatively less constrained to use the Pass. Accordingly, the subjects' elicited responses in G_2 on the Pass. reflects their preference to use the Pass. structure to any other structure. Thus, there is significant development through time in the use of the Pass. structure, manifested by the remarkable increase in the number of the Pass. VPs instances, between G_1 and G_2 . Accordingly the null hypothesis above is refuted, and Hypothesis (4) is validated.

Note to Chapter Four

¹The BA verb is passivised by prefixing the main verb with the Pass. allomorphs /ʔin/ when the verb stem is the triliteral, and /ʔit/ when the verb stem is quadriliteral (Tawfik, 1976:55).

Table (4.1) F-Value Calculated for Test-Groups

Group	Analysis of Variance					Scheffé Procedure	
	Source of Variance Transform versus VP on the Production Level	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F-Value F	Mean	Group
G1	SSR	732.04	29	25.24	7.23>1.55	8.44	1. Q2 Transform
	SSC	439.393	4	109.85	31.48>2.45 (significant)	5.4	2. Q4 Transform
	SSE	404.777	116	3.49		5.23	3. Q4 VP
	SSTO	1576.21	149			4.49	4. Q2 VP
				3.27		5. Q1 VP	
G2	SSR	231.67	29	9.71	4.28>1.55	8.79	1. Q2 Transform
	SSC	135.28	4	33.82	14.9>2.45 (significant)	7.13	2. Q4 VP
	SSE	263.63	116	2.27		6.83	3. Q4 Transform
	SSTO	680.58	149			6.24	4. Q2 VP
				6.17		5. Q1 VP	
2. i. Variable / The Recognition versus Production Levels / Transform							
G1	SSR	189.2	29	6.52	2.37>1.65	8.44	1. Q2 Transform Prod.
	SSC	202.38	2	101.19	36.8>3.15 (significant)	5.4	2. Q4 Transform Prod.
	SSE	159.21	58	2.75		5.13	3. Q5 Transform Recog.
	SSTO	550.79					
G2	SSR	114.38	29	3.94	2.76>1.65	8.79	1. Q2 Transform Prod.
	SSC	84.87	2	42.44	29.68>3.15 (significant)	6.83	2. Q4 Transform Prod.
	SSE	82.94	58	1.43		6.63	3. Q5 Transform Recog.
	SSTO	282.19					
Transform > Transform > Transform Q5 Recog. Q4 Prod. Q2 Prod.							
Transform > Transform > Transform Q5 Recog. Q4 Prod. Q2 Prod.							

Table (4.1) - Continued

Group	Analysis of Variance				Scheffé Procedure		
	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F-Value F	Mean	Group
2. ii Variable / The Recognition versus Production Level / VP							
G1	SSR	669.6	29	23.09	7.65>1.57	5.23	1. Q4 VP Prod.
	SSC	63.45	3	21.15	5.17>2.7	4.77	2. Q3 VP Recog.
	SSE	355.64	87	4.09	(significant)	4.49	3. Q2 VP Prod.
	SSTO	1088.69				3.27	4. Q1 VP Prod.
VP > VP > VP > VP							
Prod. Q1 Prod. Q2 Recog. Q3 Prod. Q4							
G2	SSR	334.51	29	11.53	4.78>1.57		
	SSC	17.45	3	5.82	2.41>2.7		
	SSE	209.94	87	2.41	(not significant)		
	SSTO	561.9					
3. Variable / Explicitness in Composition Tests							
G1	SSR	799.25	29	17.23	1.927>1.65	5.26	1. Comp. 3
	SSC	396.51	2	198.26	22.177>3.15	4.57	2. Comp. 1
	SSE	518.576	58	3.94	(significant)	0.5	3. Comp. 2
	SSTO	1414.336					
Comp. 2 > Comp. 1 > Comp. 3							
G2	SSR	715.69	29	24.68	0.345>1.65		
	SSC	95.47	2	47.74	0.667>3.15		
	SSE	4151.431	58	7.58	(not significant)		
	SSTO	4962.591					
4. Variable / Explicitness in the Whole Test							
G1	SSR	982.907	29	73.89	5.649>1.52	5.27	1. Comp. 1
	SSC	515.5	6	85.917	14.322>2.265	5.23	2. Q4
	SSE	1043.899	174	5.999	(significant)	4.77	3. Q3
	SSTO	2542.316				4.63	4. Q2
5. Comp. 3							
6. Q1							
4.27							
0.5							
7. Comp. 2							
Comp. 2 > Q1 > Comp. 3 > Q2 > Q3 > Q4 > Comp. 1							

Table (4.1) - Continued

Group	Analysis of Variance				Scheffé Procedure		
	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F-Value F	Mean	Group
G2	SSR	708.0116	29	24.415	2.953>1.52	7.17	1. Comp. 3
	SSC	124.784	6	20.797	2.516>2.26	7.13	2. Q4
	SSE	1438.392	174	8.267	(significant)	6.5	3. Q3
	SSTO	2271.222				6.25	4. Comp. 1
						6.24	5. Q2
						6.17	6. Q1
						4.64	7. Comp. 2
						Comp. 2 > Q1 > Q2 > Comp. 1 > Q3 > Q4 > Comp. 3	
5. Variable / Uses of the Passive Structure in the Composition Tests							
G1	SSR	4.518	29	0.558	5.81>1.65	0.59	1. Comp. 3
	SSC	4.137	2	2.069	21.55>3.15	0.39	2. Comp. 1
	SSE	5.555	58	0.096	(Significant)	0.07	3. Comp. 2
	SSTO	14.21					Comp. 2 > Comp. 1 > Comp. 3
G2	SSR	2.858	29	0.099	1.1186<1.65	0.58	1. Comp. 3
	SSC	2.507	2	1.253	14.158>3.15	0.25	2. Comp. 1
	SSE	5.135	58	0.0885	(significant)	0.2	3. Comp. 2
	SSTO	10.5					Comp. 2 > Comp. 1 > Comp. 3

Table (4.2) Subjects' Performance on the Transformed Obj. and the Verb Phrase

b. in Group Two

Question Type of Errors	No. of Errors in Question One	%	No. of Errors in Question Two	%	No. of Errors in Question Three	%	No. of Errors in Question Four	%	No. of Errors in Comp.1	%	No. of Errors in Comp.2	%	No. of Errors in Comp.3	%
Errors in Using the Active Instead of the Passive	82	78.09	29	35.3	76	74.50	11	23.91	18	66.66	6	37.5	24	96

incorrect, and avoided responses to each question in each group.

Table (4.6) Details of Errors in the Use of the Auxiliary *Be* and the Past Participle

Group	Question Type of Errors	No. of Errors in Question One	%	No. of Errors in Question Two	%	No. of Errors in Question Three	%	No. of Errors in Question Four	%	No. of Errors in Comp.1	%	No. of Errors in Comp.2	%	No. of Errors in Comp.3	%
G1	Omission of <i>Be</i>	0	0	2	1.85	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Omission of <i>-en</i> Morpheme	6	3.03	29	26.85	0	0	13	14.77	13	15.11	2	15.38	0	0
	Omission of <i>Be</i>	0	0	0	0	1	0.980	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
G2	Omission of <i>-en</i> Morpheme	0	0	8	9.75	0	0	5	10.86	3	11.11	4	25	0	0

Table (4.7) Errors in Using the Passive Instead of the Active

Question Group	No. of Errors in Question One	%	No. of Errors in Question Two	%	No. of Errors in Question Three	%	No. of Errors in Question Four	%	No. of Errors in Comp.1	%	No. of Errors in Comp.2	%	No. of Errors in Comp.3	%
G1	13	6.56	34	31.48	26	16.77	23	26.13	11	12.79	2	15.38	0	0
G2	23	21.90	45	54.87	25	24.50	30	65.2	6	22.22	6	37.5	1	4

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS, PEDAGOGICAL IMPLICATIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS, AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

In the light of the previous analysis, the study has come up with the following conclusions. Some are theoretical; others are practical.

5.1 Theoretical Conclusions

At the theoretical level, the study has come up with the following conclusions:

- (1) Pass. construction types are classified, in terms of the applicability of the NP-Movement rule, into transformational and lexical Pass.
- (2) The direct and indirect application of NP-Movement, through Reanalysis rule, is determined by the fact that there is, or there is no, correspondence between the Act. Pass. versions. The Reanalysis rule is, thus, responsible for classifying transformational Pass. into verbal and Pseudo-pass.
- (3) In the GB theory, the NP-Movement rule manipulates on Pass. construction types at the intraclausal level, i.e. within one clause, and at the interclausal level, i.e. within more than one clause.
- (4) There is a semantic relationship between the Subj. NPs of middle verbs, and the VPs, in terms of which some inherent

attributes in the former can promote or hamper the actualisation of the latter.

(5) Grammarians differ in defining the restrictions on the application of the Pass. rule. Some are explained in terms of syntactic constraints; others are defined semantically by means of Thematic Hierarchy Condition.

(6) Transformational Pass. types; including the verbal and pseudo-pass., are classified in terms of the application of the NP-Movement rule directly, or indirectly through Reanalysis rule. These types include: Passs. of verbs followed by single NPs, Passs. of verbs followed by *that*-clauses, Passs. of verbs followed by non-finite clauses, Passs. of double Objs., Passs. with predicative complements, Passs. followed by infinitival complements with Subjs., Passs. of causative verbs and verbs of perception, middle constructions, prepositional Passs., and idiom chunk Passs.

(7) Grammarians differ in defining the constraints on the applicability of the Pass. rule. First, the Pass. rule was restricted to transitive verbs. Then, grammarians generalised the rule to verbs, other than transitive, in terms of applying the rule to intransitive verbs that take Man Adv. By means of this constraint, passivisation can be applied to both transitive and intransitive verbs.

(8) The Pass. structure is classified, according to the presence or absence of *by*-phrase, into agentive, and agentless Pass., respectively.

(9) The Pass. is a characteristic of the academic and scientific texts, where it is used when it is desired to avoid mentioning the agent,

when it is irrelevant, unknown, or unimportant. It must, therefore, be taken as one of the best known grammatical features of the scientific language, where it is irrelevant to state who actually carried out the action. The agentless Pass. is, therefore, most commonly used in these contexts, as it constitutes around 80 percent of the Pass. clauses used in a text. Moreover, it is used in novels when writers report a series of actions that are carried out by the same persons. (Crystal, 1997:225)

5.2 Practical Conclusions

Based on the data collected from the subjects' responses to the items constructed on the basis of the theoretical framework, the following practical conclusions can be drawn from the empirical work:-

(1) Based on the statistical measurements conducted in the present study, it is found that the subjects' correct responses to the items when they are explicitly directed to the use of the Pass. are more frequent than theirs when the subjects are inexplicitly directed to perform the structure. That is, the subjects' performance on the Pass. structure is positively proportioned to explicitness of the structure.

(2) Based on the practical conclusion arrived at in point (1), at the Prod. level, the subjects' correct responses to the transformation test are proved to be more frequent than theirs elicited by any other elicitation technique implemented in this work. This is due to the overuse of transformation exercises and drills while presenting the Pass. structure in the syllabus. In other words, as the subjects get used to these exercises, they fail to produce the structure when they

are asked to identify the contexts that require the Pass., and produce the VP form.

(3) The subjects' poor awareness of the use of the Pass. structure in scientific registers, and in describing processes and actions, indicates that they find it difficult to identify the function of the Pass. as an attribute of the language of science.

(4) Based on the statistical measurements, it is indicated that the subjects' performance on the transformed Obj. is better than that on the Pass. VP. This goes true with exception to the performance of the subjects at the advanced years (G_2), in that their performance on the VP, when they are explicitly directed to produce the structure, is better than that on the transformed Obj., due to the long exposure on their part to the Pass. VP form in English.

(5) The average of the correct responses to items, measuring the subjects' receptive and productive knowledge about the transformed Obj. and the VP, indicates that they encounter much more difficulty at the Recog. level than at the Prod. level, when they are explicitly directed to perform the Pass. structure. However, the difficulty is felt to be much more at the Prod. level than that at the Recog. level, when the structure is inexplicit to the subjects, since the subjects cannot actualise their receptive knowledge about both transform and VP.

(6) At the Prod. level, and on the basis of the statistical measurements, it is concluded that the subjects' performance on the transformed Obj., when the Obj. NP is identified is better than that when it is not. This shows that the difficulty encountered in the area of the transformed Obj. stems from the identification of

the Obj. NP. that would undergo the rule; rather than the application of the rule.

(7) Iraqi EFL students at the early years at the university level face much more difficulty in the domain of the Pass. structure, at both the Recog. and Prod. levels, than those at the advanced years.

(8) Iraqi EFL students' avoidance of the Pass. structure in the guided written Comps. can be ascribed to psychological, rather than linguistic factors, such as the difficulty in producing the structure. Among these psychological factors is confidence in one's limited knowledge about the Pass.

(9) Familiarity with some construction types, in terms of their frequent use in written texts, is a crucial factor in learning or using them. Middle constructions are significantly less productive in English. The opportunity of their occurrence in an infrequent way in textbooks follows. Consequently, students encounter difficulty in using these constructions as they are unfamiliar with them.

(10) Errors in the area of Pass VP are arranged as follows (from high to low in frequency): (a) errors committed by omitting the Aux. *Be*; (b) errors in adding the Aux. *Be*; and (c) errors in the use of the past participles.

(11) Interlingual transfer is responsible for errors committed by using the Act. instead of Pass., and by omitting the Aux. *Be* that is followed by the past participle. Owing to the two different syntactic and morphological devices, implemented in English, Iraqi dialect Arabic-speaking students tend to use the Act. VP, instead of the Pass., and

omit the Aux. *Be*, as they lack such morphological devices in their native language.

Interlingual transfer, moreover, can be attributed to linguistic simplification as students find it redundant to produce the Aux. *Be*, while using the Pass. in English as they lack such an element in their native language.

(12) Iraqi EFL students avoid using Pass. types as they encounter difficulty in applying NP-Movement to these constructions whose Objs. are finite clauses. They instead, prefer to apply the rule to single NPs. This conclusion is drawn in terms of avoiding the use of Pass. of verbs followed by *that*-clauses, and replacing it by accusative Subj. Pass. (Passs. followed by infinitival complements with Subjs.).

(13) Context of learning is responsible for the subjects' failure to transform NPs, other than complements of the verbs, to the Pass. Subj. position. Teachers and instructors, when presenting the teaching items, associate the Pass. structure with the process of moving NPs that immediately follow the verbs. They, accordingly, overlook the restrictions posited on the application of NP-Movement. In addition, they entirely look at the Pass. voice category in terms of form, rather than meaning.

5.3 Pedagogical Implications and Recommendations

Based on the conclusions arrived at above, the following pedagogical implications can be outlined:-

(1) Textbook producers and teachers are to be blamed for delaying the presentation of the complex types of the Pass. constructions till the advanced years at the university level. This is in contrast to Krashen's (1981:2) model which proposes that syllabus designers and

writers of material production should present items from easy to difficult.

(2) An intensive amount of emphasis is needed on the part of teachers to demonstrate the registers in which the Pass. is prominently used as an attribute of the impersonal language. Likewise, teachers and instructors should direct the students' attention to the contexts where the Pass. is effectively used in writing.

(3) Teachers and instructors should train Iraqi EFL students to use the Pass. in free writing. Textbook writers and teachers of Comp. should cooperate to introduce students with topics that elicit the use of the Pass. in free writing.

(4) Due to the negative effect of analogy caused by the overuse of transformation exercises, which make students familiar with the mechanical change of the Pass. into Act. structure, it is recommended that exercises and drills, such as these should no longer be presented in the syllabus. Instead, completion test; short-response test, and free Comp. are in need to train students to use the Pass. VP in contexts proper.

(5) Teachers and instructors should explain the differences between the English and Colloquial Iraqi Arabic languages in explaining the Pass. structure in terms of completely different syntactic and morphological devices, i.e., NP-Movement, the Aux. *Be* and past participle in English, a change in the internal vowel pattern in Arabic.

(6) Iraqi students commit more errors in producing the Pass. structure when they are inexplicitly directed to use the structure than in recognising it. Teachers and syllabus designers should place much more emphasis on exercises which demand recognising and

producing the Pass. structure in the contexts proper, such as multiple choice test, completion test, and short-response test.

(7) Comp. teachers' task consists in preparing topics which they are required to write and that most clearly elicit the use of the Pass. structure in general; and the Pass. construction types under study, in particular. Students' Comps. are very useful for grammar teachers and instructors because they show the areas where students encounter problems in using the structure, and thus, it needs much more emphasis and explanation by teachers and instructors, i.e. they serve as a feedback for teachers.

(8) Iraqi EFL students at the early stages are in need to be introduced to the Pass. structure, in general; and the Pass. construction types under study, in particular.

(9) When presenting the Pass. structure, teachers should draw students' attention to the fact that the meaning that is expressed by the Pass. structure in English exists in Colloquial Arabic; but the two languages differ in the forms they employ to express the meaning.

(10) Students tend to avoid the Pass. structure in their writing due to inhibitions against its use. These inhibitions might be much more felt in free Comps. However, these could be alleviated through encouraging students to use the structure in their writing, starting from training them to use the Pass. structure in guided exercises, i.e. short-response question.

(11) Errors due to context of learning, and overgeneralisation in using the middle constructions necessitate that emphasis should be paid upon these constructions as they constitute the most difficult

construction types among other constructions under study on the part of students.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Research

Based on the results outlined, several suggestions for further research can be proposed:-

- (1) A study is needed to shed light upon Iraqi EFL students' effective use of the Pass. structure in free writing. A suitable technique for carrying out this study is based on Gestalt's closure perception, i.e., close-type test.
- (2) A further study is needed for investigating the order of learning any four of these constructions, in order to investigate the effect of presenting these types in the syllabus on the performance of Iraqi college students at the university level.
- (3) A further empirical study can be conducted in order to test the effect of the syllabus on Iraqi students' mastery of the basic Pass. structures, that incorporate Tns., Asp., and M. The students' achievement can, furthermore, be tested with respect to recognising and producing the Pass. infinitive, gerundive, and in negative and interrogative sentences.
- (4) A study can be carried out in order to investigate the sequence of development of Iraqi EFL students in using the constituents occurring within Pass. VP, including both the simple and complex Tns patterns. Implicational analysis can be utilised in order to assess these developmental processes.

(5) A further study is needed to investigate Iraqi EFL students' mastery of the use of transformational and lexical Pass. in the environments proper for each at both the Recog. and Prod. levels.

(6) A study is needed to investigate the difficulties Iraqi EFL students encounter in recognising and producing the constraints posited on the application of the NP-Movement rule in passivising the construction types that have been investigated in the present research.

APPENDIX 1

THE PILOT TEST VERSION SUBMITTED TO THE JURY

**UNIVERSITY OF BAGHDAD
COLLEGE OF LANGUAGES
ENGLISH DEPARTMENT**

Dear Sirs,

Enclosed is a test designed for the study entitled 'An Analytic Study of the Difficulties Faced by Iraqi EFL Students in the use of the Passive Structure'.

The test consists of two parts: the Recog. and Prod. item tests; and Comp. tests. The first part is concerned with measuring the subjects' Recog. and Prod. of the transformed Obj., and the Pass. VP. The second part, on the other hand, investigates the subjects' use of the Pass. Structure in the written Comp. It, furthermore, investigates the factors that determine the subjects' avoidance of the Pass. Structure in their writing. Both parts are designed in order to investigate the Subjects performance on the Pass. Structure when they are, or when they are not, explicitly directed to use the structure. They trace the growth in competence in using the

structure within two years of study, between the second and fourth year students of the English Department, College of Languages.

I would be grateful if you could advise me on the suitability of the test to achieve the aims above. All your comments and

modifications will be of great benefit and help to my work, and will be highly appreciated.

Yours Sincerely,

Alhan Tariq Najim

M. A. Student

UNIVERSITY OF BAGHDAD
COLLEGE OF LANGUAGES
ENGLISH DEPARTMENT

1. Name
2. College
3. Age
4. Date
5. Nationality
6. Language(s) used at home
7. How long have you been learning English?
8. Have you ever repeated a year in college?
9. Have you been taught by a native English teacher?
No ----- Yes ----- for how long? -----
10. Have you been abroad in an English speaking country?
No ----- Yes ----- for how long? -----
11. Have you participated in a course for learning English outside
school or college?
12. No ----- Yes ----- for how long? -----

The test is to measure your ability to recognize and produce the passive structure in English. We expect a serious participation on your part. We would like to thank you for your participation.

Q1. Put the verbs between brackets in the right forms.

1. He (see) by us in 1952.
2. It (believe) that Mary will fail the exam.
3. Last year, it (arrange) to attend all the lectures.
4. A letter (send) to Mary every week.
5. John (choose) as the spokesman of the group yesterday.
6. John (say) to be a good teacher.
7. They (hear) to shout something.
8. People usually buy plays written by Shakespeare, because he (read) well.
9. John (refer) to whenever a mention is made about Mary.
10. Little attention (pay) to her claim during the last meeting.

Q2. Supply the correct form of the verb between brackets, and put it in the blank space. Make sure that all these verbs should have the tense demanded by the context. Make full use of words given between brackets, so that you can get meaningful and grammatical sentences. You may need to add other words, e.g. pronouns, object or subject noun phrases, *by*, *to* or *that*.

1. How is an egg fried? (over the cooker- the frying pan- place (v.)/ a piece of fat- melt(v.) – with it)
2. Why do you come late every day? (the streets- crowd(v.))
3. Report any comment you heard about Mr. William yesterday. (Mr. William- say- be an influential- gentleman)
4. How do you feel now about the new policy, John? (disappoint (v.)- that the council have adopted that policy)
5. What was decided to be done after the dinner? (decide- go- to Basrah)

6. what was their plan for the future after they got married?
(arrange- leave- for London)
7. John died. His parents are in London. Did you call them?(send a letter)
8. Do they have enough money? (give money- them they- their uncle who lives in London)
9. How do people usually find this place?(find- the place- Comfortable)
10. Did you find the spelling of the word correct? (it- find- misspelt)
11. State your opinion about John. (John- believe- honest- be)
12. Tell where his birth was. (think- bear- in England)
13. Did you join Mary and John? (walk together- I let)
14. What were his remarks after he had finished the reading of the whole chapter? (make- rewrite- the chapter)
15. Why did you buy meat from this store yesterday? (the meat which I bought from this store – easily-cook)
16. Why do you always buy books written by Shakespeare? (Shakespeare- well- read)
17. What happened to John's back? (John- ran after- Bill/ and he- him- hit- at the back)
18. Were Christopher Columbus and his men the first to discover America? (Norman land on the coast of North America in 10th or 11th century)
19. Did he neglect your speech? (take- note of- all what- say to him- he)
20. Do they support his proposal? (a great account- take of- all his suggestions).

Q.3 Study the following sentences, and encircle the letter of the correct choice of the verb form between brackets.

1. The week end's shopping (do) by Peter every month.
 - a. done
 - b. is doing
 - c. is done
 - d. are done
2. It (expect)that Mary will come.
 - a. expected
 - b. is expected
 - c. is expecting
 - d. was expecting
3. It (decide) to meet in London.
 - a. was decided
 - b. decided
 - c. is deciding
 - d. decides
4. A dress (buy) for Mary every year.
 - a. bought
 - b. buys
 - c. is bought
 - d. is buying
5. John (appoint) as an ambassador last year.
 - a. appoints
 - b. appointed
 - c. was appointing
 - d. was appointed
6. The student(assume) to know some French.
 - a. assume
 - b. assumed
 - c. is assumed
 - d. is assuming
7. The air(let) out of the tyres; and they could not move the car.
 - a. was let
 - b. let
 - c. lets
 - d. were let
8. The meat that you bought yesterday was good. It (cook) easily.
 - a. has been cooked
 - b. is cooked
 - c. was cooked
 - d. cooked
9. The proposal (agree) by the committee.
 - a. is agreed on
 - b. is agreed to
 - c. agreed on
 - d. agreed
10. Her beauty (make advantage of) when she was in Paris.
 - a. is made advantage
 - b. make advantage
 - c. was made advantage of
 - d. made advantage of

Q.4 Change the following sentences, if possible, into passive. Use *by* (the agent) only when it is needed to complete the sentence. Make full use of the auxiliary and the past participles between the brackets, given at the end of each sentence when you transform the sentence into passive.

1. Somebody shut the door in my face yesterday. (was shut)
2. People expect Mary will win. (is expected)
3. He agreed to start working. (was agreed)
4. We always pay her the rent in the middle of the month. (is paid)
5. A man with a scar on his face mistook Mary for Jean.(was mistaken)
6. they believe Susan to be the most beautiful girl in the college. (is believed)
- 7.They let us go. (were let)
8. Science fictions sell easily. (are sold)
9. Most of us only glance through these magazines. (are glanced)
- 10.We put an end to this fuss yesterday. (was put)

Q5. State whether the structure of the following sentences are correct or incorrect; and correct the wrong ones.

- 1.All afternoon is played by few children.
2. It was decided to leave for London.
- 3.Mary was thought that would fail he exam.
- 4.A new chair is usually made for John.
- 5.Chairman was elected John.
- 6.They were seen go out.
7. My students are considered to be conscientious.

8. This book sells easily these days.

9. The office is worked at by a lot of people.

10. Dinner was drunk Pepsi after by Bill.

Q1. Make use of the notes given below to talk about what happened to the cyclist, Aisha. Your paragraph(s) should be no less than 100- 150 words in length.

-Aisha left school.

-Bicycling home,

-could she finish her homework before lunch?

(1)(Causes of the accident)

-ride- past- road

- main road- no traffic

-driver in a hurry

-bus- not control

(2)(Accident)

-injured –fall

-bus- Aisha- hit

(3)(The effects)

-injured- Aisha

-damage- bicycle

(4)(The driver's standpoint against the accident)

-driver- help- stop

-telephone- hospital

-fast arrival of red crescent ambulance

-assistants- carry- stretcher- carefully

(5)(In the hospital)

-Aisha- admit- to hospital casualty department

-report- bad cut on her left hand- as well

-but X-ray showed no broken bones on her left hand

-Anti-tetanus injection, antiseptic cream, and three stitches- require

(6)(Only after effect): a slight headache

-leave alone in the room thinking

-left hand- What about her English homework?

Q2. Describe what happens when you post a letter in the post office.

Make sure that you touch upon the following points, provided that your paragraph(s) should be no less than 100- 150 words in length.

- 1.Posting a letter
- 2.Emptying the post box.
- 3.Postmarking the stamps at the post office.
- 4.Sorting the letters into different towns.
- 5.Loading the mail into the train.
- 6.Unloading the mail bags after their journey.
- 7.Taking the bags to the post office.
- 8.Sorting the letters into different streets.
- 9.Delivering the letters.

Q3. Use the verbs given in the flow- chart below to write your paragraph(s), provided that it/ they should be no less than (100- 150) words in length.

Raw- rubber

APPENDIX 2

SUBJECTS' PERFORMANCE ON THE PILOT TEST VERSION

(1) The Recog. Tests

No.	X(test)	Y(retest)	XY	X ²	Y ²
1	11	9	99	121	81
2	8	11	88	64	121
3	2	8	16	4	64
4	8	9	72	64	81
5	4	7	28	16	49
6	10	8	80	100	64
7	17	16	272	289	156
8	12	9	108	144	81
9	11	11	121	121	121
10	9	11	99	81	121
11	11	5	55	121	25
12	6	7	42	36	49
Σ	109	111	1080	1161	1113

(2) The Prod. Tests

No.	X(test)	Y(retest)	XY	X ²	Y ²
1	26	25	650	676	625
2	29	30	870	841	900
3	29	18	522	841	324
4	18	21	378	324	441
5	19	12	228	361	144
6	10	14	140	100	196
7	53	53	2809	2809	2809
8	37	41	1517	1369	1681
9	18	20	360	324	400
10	33	33	1089	1089	1089
11	21	30	630	441	900
12	20	21	420	400	441
Σ	313	318	9613	9575	9950

(3)The Whole Tests

No.	X(test)	Y(retest)	XY	X ²	Y ²
1	37	34	1258	1369	1156
2	37	41	1517	1369	1681
3	31	26	806	961	676
4	26	30	780	676	900
5	23	19	437	529	361
6	20	22	440	400	484
7	70	69	4830	4900	4761
8	49	50	2450	2401	2500
9	29	31	899	841	961
10	42	44	1848	1764	1936
11	32	35	1120	1024	1225
12	26	28	728	646	784
Σ	422	429	17113	16910	17425

APPENDIX 3

THE TEST FINAL VERSION

Q1. Put the verbs between brackets in the correct forms in order to get grammatical and meaningful sentences. Please make no

other changes in the other parts of the sentences.

1. He (see) by us in 1952.
2. It (believe) that Mary will fail the exam.
3. Last year, it (arrange) to attend all the lectures.
4. A letter (send) to Mary every week.
5. John (choose) as the spokesman of the group yesterday.
6. John (say) to be a good teacher.
7. They (hear) to shout something.
8. People usually buy plays written by Shakespeare, because he (read) well.
9. John (refer) to whenever a mention is made about Mary.
10. Little attention (pay) to her claim during the last meeting.

Q2. *Reaarange* the words between brackets when you answer the following questions. You may need to add *object* or *subject*.

You need to change the form of the verbs to get the answers grammatical and meaningful.

1. How is an egg fried? (over the fire - the pan- place (v.)/ and- a piece of fat- melt(v.) – with it)
2. Why do you come late every day? (the streets- crowd(v.))
3. Report any comment you heard about Mr. William yesterday.(to be an influential gentleman- Mr. William- say)
4. How do you feel now about the new policy, John? (disappoint (v.)- that the council have adopted that policy)
5. What was decided to be done after the dinner? (decide- to go to Basrah)
6. what was their plan for the future after they got married?(it- arrange- leave for London)
7. John died. His parents are in London. How did they know about his death?(send a letter)

8. According to my knowledge, he lost all the money his uncle had sent to him. (give more money- his uncle who lives in London)

Yes, but.....

9. what is your opinion of this place?(find- the place- Comfortable)

10. Was the spelling of the word correct? (it- find- missplelt)

11. State your opinion about John. (John- believe- to be honest)

12. Tell where his birth was. (think- to be born in England)

13. Did anybody join Mary and John? (walk together- I let)

14. What were his remarks after he had finished the reading of your chapter? (make- rewrite- the whole chapter)

15. Why did you buy meat from this store yesterday? (the meat which I bought from this store – easily-cook)

Because

16. Why do you always buy books written by Shakespeare? (Shakespeare's books- well- read)

Because

17. What happened to John's back? (at the back- hit)

John was followed by Bill, and he(John)

18. Were Christopher Columbus and his men the first to discover America? (the coast of North America- in 10th or 11th century- Norman- land on)

19. Did he neglect your speech? (take- note- of- all what I say to him)

20. Do they support his proposal? (a great account- take of- all his suggestions).

Q.3 Study the following sentences, and encircle the letter of the correct choice of the verb form between brackets.

1. The week end's shopping (do) by Peter every month.
 - a. done
 - b. is doing
 - c. is done
 - d. are done
2. It (expect)that Mary will come.
 - a. expected
 - b. is expected
 - c. is expecting
 - d. was expecting
3. It (decide) to meet in London.
 - a. was decided
 - b. decided
 - c. is deciding
 - d. decides
4. A dress (buy) for Mary every year.
 - a. bought
 - b. buys
 - c. is bought
 - d. is buying
5. John (appoint) as an ambassador last year.
 - a. appoints
 - b. appointed
 - c. was appointing
 - d. was appointed
6. The student(assume) to know some French.
 - a. assume
 - b. assumed
 - c. is assumed
 - d. is assuming
7. The air(let) out of the tyres; and they could not move the car.
 - a. was let
 - b. let
 - c. lets
 - d. were let
8. The meat that you bought yesterday was good. It (cook) easily.
 - a. has been cooked
 - b. is cooked
 - c. was cooked
 - d. cooked
9. The proposal (agree) by the committee.
 - a. is agreed on
 - b. is agreed to
 - c. agreed on
 - d. agreed
10. Her beauty (make advantage of) when she was in Paris.
 - a. is made advantage
 - b. make advantage
 - c. was made advantage of
 - d. made advantage of

Q.4 Change the following sentences, if possible, into passive

1. Somebody shut the door in my face yesterday.
2. People expect Mary will win.
3. He agreed to start working.
4. We always pay her the rent in the middle of the month.
5. A man with a scar on his face mistook Mary for Jean.
6. they believe Susan to be the most beautiful girl in the college
- 7.They let us go.
8. Science fictions sell easily.
9. Most of us only glance through these magazines.
- 10.We put an end to this fuss yesterday.

Q5. State whether the structure of the following sentences are correct or incorrect; and correct the wrong ones.

- 1.All afternoon is played by few children.
2. It was decided to leave for London.
- 3.Mary was thought that would fail he exam.
- 4.A new chair is usually made for John.
- 5.Chairman was elected John.
- 6.They were seen go out.
7. My students are considered to be conscientious.
8. This book sells easily these days.
9. The office is worked at by a lot of people.
10. Dinner was drunk Pepsi after by Bill.

Q1. Make use of the notes given below to talk about what happened to the cyclist, Aisha. Your paragraph(s) should be no less than

100- 150 words in length.

-Aisha left school.

-Bicycling home,

-could she finish her homework before lunch?

(1)(Causes of the accident)

-ride- past- road

- main road- no traffic

-driver in a hurry

-bus- not control

(2)(Accident)

-accident –fall

-bus- Aisha- hit

(3)(The effects)

-injured- Aisha

-damage- bicycle

(4)(The driver's standpoint against the accident)

-driver- help- stop

-telephone- hospital

-fast arrival of red crescent ambulance

-assistants- carry- stretcher- carefully

(5)(In the hospital)

-Aisha- admit- to hospital casualty department

-report- bad cut on her left hand- as well

-but X-ray showed no broken bones on her left hand

-Anti-tetanus injection, antiseptic cream, and three stitches- require

(6)(Only after effect): a slight headache

-leave alone in the room thinking

-left hand- What about her English homework?

Q2. Describe what happens when you post a letter in the post office.

Make sure that you touch upon the following points, provided that your paragraph(s) should be no less than 100- 150 words in length.

- 1.Posting a letter
- 2.Emptying the post box.
- 3.Postmarking the stamps at the post office.
- 4.Sorting the letters into different towns.
- 5.Loading the mail into the train.
- 6.Unloading the mail bags after their journey.
- 7.Taking the bags to the post office.
- 8.Sorting the letters into different streets.
- 9.Delivering the letters.

Q3. Use the verbs given in the flow- chart below to write your paragraph(s); provided that it/ they should be no less than (100- 150) words in length.

Raw- rubber

APPENDIX 4

SUBJECTS' PERFORMANCE ON THE COMPOSITION TESTS

Group 1															
Subject	Comp. 1					Comp. 2					Comp. 3				
	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio
	1	114	6	0.53	1	1.67	112	0	0	0	0	60	0	0	0
2	200	3	0.15	1	3.33	107	0	0	0	0	73	5	0.68	5	4
3	112	6	0.54	2	3.33	92	0	0	0	0	54	6	1.11	6	1.67
4	168	6	0.88	5	8.33	71	1	0.14	0	0	75	5	0.67	5	10
5	153	2	0.13	0	0	49	0	0	0	0	63	3	0.48	3	3.33
6	303	7	0.23	7	10	172	0	0	0	0	96	4	0.42	4	7.5
7	220	6	0.27	6	10	91	0	0	0	0	67	6	0.9	6	10
8	238	4	0.17	2	5	80	0	0	0	0	76	0	0	0	0
9	213	9	0.42	5	5.56	104	0	0	0	0	58	6	1.03	6	10
10	169	9	0.53	6	6.67	75	0	0	0	0	66	3	0.46	3	10
11	176	6	0.34	5	8.33	74	0	0	0	0	55	6	1.09	6	10
12	260	5	0.19	2	4	104	1	0.1	0	0	61	0	0	0	0
13	193	7	0.36	2	2.86	87	1	0.11	0	0	75	6	0.8	6	5
14	247	8	0.32	8	10	69	0	0	0	0	140	5	0.36	5	10
15	163	7	0.43	0	0	85	2	0.21	0	0	60	4	0.67	4	2.5
16	122	5	0.41	1	2	118	0	0	0	0	96	0	0	0	0

1	114	6	0.53	1	1.67	112	0	0	0	0	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	200	3	0.15	1	3.33	107	0	0	0	0	73	0	0	0	0.68	5	5	4	0
3	112	6	0.54	2	3.33	92	0	0	0	0	54	0	0	0	1.11	6	6	1.67	0
4	168	6	0.88	5	8.33	71	1	0.14	0	0	75	0	0	0	0.67	5	5	10	0
5	153	2	0.13	0	0	49	0	0	0	0	63	0	0	0	0.48	3	3	3.33	0
6	303	7	0.23	7	10	172	0	0	0	0	96	0	0	0	0.42	4	4	7.5	0
7	220	6	0.27	6	10	91	0	0	0	0	67	0	0	0	0.9	6	6	10	0
8	238	4	0.17	2	5	80	0	0	0	0	76	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	213	9	0.42	5	5.56	104	0	0	0	0	58	0	0	0	1.03	6	6	10	0
10	169	9	0.53	6	6.67	75	0	0	0	0	66	0	0	0	0.46	3	3	10	0
11	176	6	0.34	5	8.33	74	0	0	0	0	55	0	0	0	1.09	6	6	10	0
12	260	5	0.19	2	4	104	1	0.1	0	0	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	193	7	0.36	2	2.86	87	1	0.11	0	0	75	0	0	0	0.8	6	6	5	0
14	247	8	0.32	8	10	69	0	0	0	0	140	0	0	0	0.36	5	5	10	0
15	163	7	0.43	0	0	85	2	0.21	0	0	60	0	0	0	0.67	4	4	2.5	0
16	122	5	0.41	1	2	118	0	0	0	0	96	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	131	4	0.31	3	7.5	97	0	0	0	0	11.2	0	0	0	0.45	5	5	10	0
18	135	2	0.15	1	5	82	0	0	0	0	68	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	158	3	0.19	0	0	84	0	0	0	0	70	0	0	0	0.29	2	2	10	0
20	176	3	0.17	1	3.33	86	0	0	0	0	85	0	0	0	0.59	5	5	0	0
21	199	5	0.25	3	6	93	0	0	0	0	62	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	132	4	0.3	0	0	39	2	0.51	0	0	58	0	0	0	1.03	6	6	10	0

Subject	Group 2														
	Comp. 1				Comp. 2				Comp. 3						
	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio		
1	111	3	0.27	2	6.67	71	0	0	0	0	170	6	0.35	6	10
2	243	1	0.08	1	5	78	8	1.03	2	2.5	89	6	0.67	6	10
3	147	3	0.2	2	6.67	87	0	0	0	0	77	4	0.52	4	10
4	97	1	0.1	1	10	70	1	0.14	1	10	71	7	0.99	7	10
5	129	2	0.16	2	10	76	0	0	0	0	66	6	0.91	1	1.67
6	106	6	0.57	6	10	75	2	0.27	0	0	96	1	0.1	1	10
7	201	5	0.25	3	6	76	4	0.53	4	10	63	5	0.79	5	10
8	207	3	0.14	1	3.33	92	0	0	0	0	88	6	0.68	3	5
9	121	5	0.41	5	10	91	5	0.55	3	6	84	6	0.71	6	10
10	214	7	0.33	7	10	92	3	0.33	2	6.67	76	5	0.66	5	10
11	156	4	0.26	4	10	99	2	0.2	1	5	50	0	0	0	0
12	213	2	0.09	1	5	122	1	0.08	1	10	19	0	0	0	0
13	113	2	0.18	2	10	82	0	0	0	0	61	5	0.82	1	2
14	167	5	0.3	4	8	90	2	0.22	2	10	50	0	0	0	0
15	82	0	0	0	0	79	0	0	0	0	62	6	0.97	6	10
16	119	3	0.25	3	10	128	3	0.23	3	10	115	5	0.43	5	10

GROUP ONE

Subjects	Ratio of Words to Pass in Comp. 1	Ratio of Words to Pass in Comp. 2	Ratio of Words to Pass in Comp. 3	Ratio of Pass to Correct Pass, in Comp. 1	Ratio of Pass to Correct Pass, in Comp. 2	Ratio of Pass to Correct Pass, in Comp. 3	No. of Correct responses to VP Q1	No. of Correct responses to Pass, of the first type Q1	No. of Correct Responses to the transformed Obj. Q2	No. of Correct responses to VP Q2	No. of Correct responses to Pass, of the first type Q2	No. of Pass, used of the first type Q2	No. of Pass, used in Q2	No. of Correct responses to VP Q3	No. of Correct responses to Pass, of the first type Q3	No. of Correct responses to the transformed Obj. Q4	No. of Correct responses to VP Q4	No. of Correct responses to Pass, of the first type Q4	No. of Correct responses to the transformed Obj. Q5
1	0.53	0	0	1.67	0	0	1	0	7	3	0	0	7	2	0	6	4	0	7
2	0.15	0	0.68	3.33	0	4	7	1	9	5	0	0	9	7	1	6	9	1	4
3	0.54	0	1.11	3.33	0	1.67	1	0	4	3	0	0	5	3	0	4	3	0	5
4	0.88	0.14	0.67	8.33	0	10	8	1	9	6	1	1	9	7	1	8	9	1	6
5	0.13	0	0.48	0	0	3.33	1	0	7	1	0	2	7	5	0	5	3	1	7
6	0.23	0	0.42	10	0	7.5	9	1	20	18	2	2	20	9	1	10	9	1	6
7	0.27	0	0.9	10	0	10	9	1	9	6	2	2	10	9	1	8	9	1	4
8	0.17	0	0	5	0	0	1	0	7	3	1	2	7	9	1	7	8	1	4
9	0.42	0	1.03	5.56	0	0	0	0	5	5	0	1	8	2	0	7	9	1	4
10	0.53	0	0.46	6.67	0	10	2	1	5	0	0	1	5	6	1	9	9	1	4
11	0.34	0	1.09	8.33	0	10	9	1	9	7	1	1	9	9	1	6	7	1	6
12	0.19	0.1	0	4	0	0	3	1	4	1	0	0	4	8	0	6	6	0	5

1	0.53	0	0	1.67	0	0	0	1	0	7	3	0	0	7	2	0	6	4	0	7
2	0.15	0	0.68	3.33	0	4	7	1	1	9	5	0	0	9	7	1	6	9	1	4
3	0.54	0	1.11	3.33	0	1.67	1	0	0	4	3	0	0	5	3	0	4	3	0	5
4	0.88	0.14	0.67	8.33	0	10	8	1	1	9	6	1	1	9	7	1	8	9	1	6
5	0.13	0	0.48	0	0	3.33	1	0	2	7	1	0	2	7	5	0	5	3	1	7
6	0.23	0	0.42	10	0	7.5	9	1	2	20	18	2	2	20	9	1	10	9	1	6
7	0.27	0	0.9	10	0	10	9	1	1	9	6	2	2	10	9	1	8	9	1	4
8	0.17	0	0	5	0	0	1	0	2	7	3	1	2	7	9	1	7	8	1	4
9	0.42	0	1.03	5.56	0	0	0	0	1	5	5	0	1	8	2	0	7	9	1	4
10	0.53	0	0.46	6.67	0	10	2	1	1	5	0	0	1	5	6	1	9	9	1	4
11	0.34	0	1.09	8.33	0	10	9	1	1	9	7	1	1	9	9	1	6	7	1	6
12	0.19	0.1	0	4	0	0	3	1	0	4	1	0	0	4	8	0	6	6	0	5
13	0.36	0.11	0.8	2.86	0	5	3	0	2	10	7	1	2	11	4	0	7	7	1	5
14	0.32	0	0.36	10	0	10	10	1	1	10	7	0	1	10	8	1	8	9	1	5
15	0.43	0.21	0.67	0	0	2.5	1	0	2	6	2	0	2	7	2	0	7	8	1	3
16	0.41	0	0	2	0	0	4	1	2	6	1	0	2	9	3	1	6	6	0	4
17	0.31	0	0.45	7.5	0	10	5	1	1	8	7	1	1	8	6	1	4	3	1	8
18	0.15	0	0	5	0	0	1	0	2	5	1	0	2	11	2	1	4	2	1	6
19	0.19	0	0.29	0	0	10	0	0	1	7	1	0	1	9	5	0	0	0	0	4
20	0.17	0	0.59	3.33	0	0	1	0	2	10	3	0	2	13	3	0	5	2	1	5
21	0.25	0	0	6	0	0	1	0	1	4	0	0	1	10	0	0	0	0	0	5
22	0.3	0.51	1.03	0	0	10	0	0	2	12	9	2	2	17	5	0	5	3	1	3

GROUP TWO

Subjects	Ratio of Words to Pass. in Comp. 1	Ratio of Words to Pass. in Comp. 2	Ratio of Words to Pass. in Comp. 3	Ratio of Pass. to Correct Pass. in Comp. 1	Ratio of Pass. to Correct Pass. in Comp. 2	Ratio of Pass. to Correct Pass. in Comp. 3	No. of Correct responses to VP Q1	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q1	No. of Correct Responses to the transformed Obj. Q2	No. of Correct responses to VP Q2	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q2	No. of Pass. used of the first type Q2	No. of Pass. used in Q2	No. of Correct responses to VP Q3	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q3	No. of Correct responses to the transformed Obj. Q4	No. of Correct responses to VP Q4	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q4	No. of Correct responses to the transformed Obj. Q5
31	0.27	0	0.35	6.67	0	10	8	0	10	9	1	1	11	5	1	9	9	1	7
32	0.08	1.03	0.67	5	2.5	10	7	1	10	8	1	1	11	8	1	6	9	1	8
33	0.2	0	0.52	6.67	0	10	6	0	5	3	1	1	6	7	1	5	5	1	9
34	0.1	0.14	0.99	10	10	10	5	1	10	8	1	1	15	8	1	7	7	1	6
35	0.16	0	0.91	10	0	1.67	0	0	5	0	0	1	6	2	0	5	3	1	4
36	0.57	0.27	0.1	10	0	10	6	0	10	7	1	1	11	7	1	6	7	1	8
37	0.25	0.53	0.79	6	10	10	4	0	9	6	1	1	9	7	1	4	3	1	6
38	0.14	0	0.68	3.33	0	5	4	0	8	5	1	1	8	5	1	6	8	1	6
39	0.41	0.55	0.71	10	6	10	3	0	9	6	1	1	9	6	1	7	7	1	8
40	0.33	0.33	0.66	10	6.67	10	4	0	12	10	1	1	12	5	0	8	8	1	8
41	0.26	0.2	0	10	5	0	10	1	13	11	1	2	14	8	1	8	9	1	8
42	0.09	0.08	0	5	10	0	8	1	10	8	1	2	17	6	1	3	5	1	2

31	0.27	0	0.35	6.67	0	10	8	0	10	9	1	1	11	5	1	9	9	1	7
32	0.08	1.03	0.67	5	2.5	10	7	1	10	8	1	1	11	8	1	6	9	1	8
33	0.2	0	0.52	6.67	0	10	6	0	5	3	1	1	6	7	1	5	5	1	9
34	0.1	0.14	0.99	10	10	10	5	1	10	8	1	1	15	8	1	7	7	1	6
35	0.16	0	0.91	10	0	1.67	0	0	5	0	0	1	6	2	0	5	3	1	4
36	0.57	0.27	0.1	10	0	10	6	0	10	7	1	1	11	7	1	6	7	1	8
37	0.25	0.53	0.79	6	10	10	4	0	9	6	1	1	9	7	1	4	3	1	6
38	0.14	0	0.68	3.33	0	5	4	0	8	5	1	1	8	5	1	6	8	1	6
39	0.41	0.55	0.71	10	6	10	3	0	9	6	1	1	9	6	1	7	7	1	8
40	0.33	0.33	0.66	10	6.67	10	4	0	12	10	1	1	12	5	0	8	8	1	8
41	0.26	0.2	0	10	5	0	10	1	13	11	1	2	14	8	1	8	9	1	8
42	0.09	0.08	0	5	10	0	8	1	10	8	1	2	17	6	1	3	5	1	2
43	0.18	0	0.82	10	0	2	3	1	8	7	2	2	10	4	0	8	5	1	8
44	0.3	0.22	0	8	10	0	4	0	6	3	1	1	6	5	0	9	9	1	7
45	0	0	0.97	0	0	10	6	1	11	12	0	2	18	9	1	6	8	1	8
46	0.25	0.23	0.43	10	10	10	10	1	6	5	1	1	7	8	1	9	9	1	5
47	0.45	0	0.69	10	0	10	8	1	11	9	1	1	11	8	0	7	9	1	6
48	0.25	0	1.04	10	0	10	9	1	11	9	1	2	12	9	1	7	8	1	7
49	0.27	0	0.66	6.67	0	10	7	1	8	7	1	1	8	8	1	7	6	1	6
50	0.32	0.09	0.94	10	10	8.75	8	1	12	7	0	2	12	8	1	8	9	1	8
51	0.27	0.27	2	8.33	10	10	9	1	12	10	1	2	13	8	1	7	7	1	7
52	0.28	0	0	10	0	0	9	0	8	7	2	2	9	9	1	8	8	1	6

APPENDIX 5

SUBJECTS' PERFORMANCE ON THE WHOLE TEST

Subject	Group 1														
	Comp. 1				Comp. 2				Comp. 3						
	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio
1	114	6	0.53	1	1.67	112	0	0	0	0	60	0	0	0	0
2	200	3	0.15	1	3.33	107	0	0	0	0	73	5	0.68	5	4
3	112	6	0.54	2	3.33	92	0	0	0	0	54	6	1.11	6	1.67
4	168	6	0.88	5	8.33	71	1	0.14	0	0	75	5	0.67	5	10
5	153	2	0.13	0	0	49	0	0	0	0	63	3	0.48	3	3.33
6	303	7	0.23	7	10	172	0	0	0	0	96	4	0.42	4	7.5
7	220	6	0.27	6	10	91	0	0	0	0	67	6	0.9	6	10
8	238	4	0.17	2	5	80	0	0	0	0	76	0	0	0	0
9	213	9	0.42	5	5.56	104	0	0	0	0	58	6	1.03	6	10
10	169	9	0.53	6	6.67	75	0	0	0	0	66	3	0.46	3	10
11	176	6	0.34	5	8.33	74	0	0	0	0	55	6	1.09	6	10
12	260	5	0.19	2	4	104	1	0.1	0	0	61	0	0	0	0
13	193	7	0.36	2	2.86	87	1	0.11	0	0	75	6	0.8	6	5
14	247	8	0.32	8	10	69	0	0	0	0	140	5	0.36	5	10
15	163	7	0.43	0	0	85	2	0.21	0	0	60	4	0.67	4	2.5
16	122	5	0.41	1	2	118	0	0	0	0	96	0	0	0	0

Group 2																		
Subject	Comp. 1						Comp. 2						Comp. 3					
	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio	No. of Correct Pass.	Ratio	No. of Words	No. of Pass.	Ratio
1	111	3	0.27	2	6.67	71	0	0	0	0	170	6	0.35	6	10			
2	243	1	0.08	1	5	78	8	1.03	2	2.5	89	6	0.67	6	10			
3	147	3	0.2	2	6.67	87	0	0	0	0	77	4	0.52	4	10			
4	97	1	0.1	1	10	70	1	0.14	1	10	71	7	0.99	7	10			
5	129	2	0.16	2	10	76	0	0	0	0	66	6	0.91	1	1.67			
6	106	6	0.57	6	10	75	2	0.27	0	0	96	1	0.1	1	10			
7	201	5	0.25	3	6	76	4	0.53	4	10	63	5	0.79	5	10			
8	207	3	0.14	1	3.33	92	0	0	0	0	88	6	0.68	3	5			
9	121	5	0.41	5	10	91	5	0.55	3	6	84	6	0.71	6	10			
10	214	7	0.33	7	10	92	3	0.33	2	6.67	76	5	0.66	5	10			
11	156	4	0.26	4	10	99	2	0.2	1	5	50	0	0	0	0			
12	213	2	0.09	1	5	122	1	0.08	1	10	19	0	0	0	0			
13	113	2	0.18	2	10	82	0	0	0	0	61	5	0.82	1	2			
14	167	5	0.3	4	8	90	2	0.22	2	10	50	0	0	0	0			
15	82	0	0	0	0	79	0	0	0	0	62	6	0.97	6	10			
16	119	3	0.25	3	10	128	3	0.23	3	10	115	5	0.43	5	10			

GROUP ONE

Subjects	Ratio of Words to Pass in Comp. 1	Ratio of Words to Pass in Comp. 2	Ratio of Words to Pass in Comp. 3	Ratio of Pass. to Correct Pass. in Comp. 1	Ratio of Pass. to Correct Pass. in Comp. 2	Ratio of Pass. to Correct Pass. in Comp. 3	No. of Correct responses to VP Q1	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q1	No. of Correct Responses to the transformed Obl. Q2	No. of Correct responses to VP Q2	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q2	No. of Pass. used of the first type Q2	No. of Pass. used in Q2	No. of Correct responses to VP Q3	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q3	No. of Correct responses to the transformed Obl. Q4	No. of Correct responses to VP Q4	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q4	No. of Correct responses to the transformed Obj. Q5
1	0.53	0	0	1.67	0	0	1	0	7	3	0	0	7	2	0	6	4	0	7
2	0.15	0	0.68	3.33	0	4	7	1	9	5	0	0	9	7	1	6	9	1	4
3	0.54	0	1.11	3.33	0	1.67	1	0	4	3	0	0	5	3	0	4	3	0	5
4	0.88	0.14	0.67	8.33	0	10	8	1	9	6	1	1	9	7	1	8	9	1	6
5	0.13	0	0.48	0	0	3.33	1	0	7	1	0	2	7	5	0	5	3	1	7
6	0.23	0	0.42	10	0	7.5	9	1	20	18	2	2	20	9	1	10	9	1	6
7	0.27	0	0.9	10	0	10	9	1	9	6	2	2	10	9	1	8	9	1	4
8	0.17	0	0	5	0	0	1	0	7	3	1	2	7	9	1	7	8	1	4
9	0.42	0	1.03	5.56	0	0	0	0	5	5	0	1	8	2	0	7	9	1	4
10	0.53	0	0.46	6.67	0	10	2	1	5	0	0	1	5	6	1	9	9	1	4
11	0.34	0	1.09	8.33	0	10	9	1	9	7	1	1	9	9	1	6	7	1	6
12	0.19	0.1	0	4	0	0	3	1	4	1	0	0	4	8	0	6	6	0	5

GROUP TWO

Subjects	Ratio of Words to Pass. in Comp. 1	Ratio of Words to Pass. in Comp. 2	Ratio of Words to Pass. in Comp. 3	Ratio of Pass. to Correct Pass. in Comp. 1	Ratio of Pass. to Correct Pass. in Comp. 2	Ratio of Pass. to Correct Pass. in Comp. 3	No. of Correct responses to VP Q1	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q1	No. of Correct Responses to the transformed Obj. Q2	No. of Correct responses to VP Q2	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q2	No. of Pass. used of the first type Q2	No. of Pass. used in Q2	No. of Correct responses to VP Q3	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q3	No. of Correct responses to the transformed Obj. Q4	No. of Correct responses to VP Q4	No. of Correct responses to Pass. of the first type Q4	No. of Correct responses to the transformed Obj. Q5
31	0.27	0	0.35	6.67	0	10	8	0	10	9	1	1	11	5	1	9	9	1	7
32	0.08	1.03	0.67	5	2.5	10	7	1	10	8	1	1	11	8	1	6	9	1	8
33	0.2	0	0.52	6.67	0	10	6	0	5	3	1	1	6	7	1	5	5	1	9
34	0.1	0.14	0.99	10	10	10	5	1	10	8	1	1	15	8	1	7	7	1	6
35	0.16	0	0.91	10	0	1.67	0	0	5	0	0	1	6	2	0	5	3	1	4
36	0.57	0.27	0.1	10	0	10	6	0	10	7	1	1	11	7	1	6	7	1	8
37	0.25	0.53	0.79	6	10	10	4	0	9	6	1	1	9	7	1	4	3	1	6
38	0.14	0	0.68	3.33	0	5	4	0	8	5	1	1	8	5	1	6	8	1	6
39	0.41	0.55	0.71	10	6	10	3	0	9	6	1	1	9	6	1	7	7	1	8
40	0.33	0.33	0.66	10	6.67	10	4	0	12	10	1	1	12	5	0	8	8	1	8
41	0.26	0.2	0	10	5	0	10	1	13	11	1	2	14	8	1	8	9	1	8
42	0.09	0.08	0	5	10	0	8	1	10	8	1	2	17	6	1	3	5	1	2

31	0.27	0	0.35	6.67	0	10	8	0	10	9	1	1	1	11	5	1	9	1	7
32	0.08	1.03	0.67	5	2.5	10	7	1	10	8	1	1	1	11	8	1	9	1	8
33	0.2	0	0.52	6.67	0	10	6	0	5	3	1	1	1	6	7	1	5	1	9
34	0.1	0.14	0.99	10	10	10	5	1	10	8	1	1	1	15	8	1	7	1	6
35	0.16	0	0.91	10	0	1.67	0	0	5	0	0	1	1	6	2	0	3	1	4
36	0.57	0.27	0.1	10	0	10	6	0	10	7	1	1	1	11	7	1	6	1	8
37	0.25	0.53	0.79	6	10	10	4	0	9	6	1	1	1	9	7	1	3	1	6
38	0.14	0	0.68	3.33	0	5	4	0	8	5	1	1	1	8	5	1	8	1	6
39	0.41	0.55	0.71	10	6	10	3	0	9	6	1	1	1	9	6	1	7	1	8
40	0.33	0.33	0.66	10	6.67	10	4	0	12	10	1	1	1	12	5	0	8	1	8
41	0.26	0.2	0	10	5	0	10	1	13	11	1	2	2	14	8	1	9	1	8
42	0.09	0.08	0	5	10	0	8	1	10	8	1	2	2	17	6	1	5	1	2
43	0.18	0	0.82	10	0	2	3	1	8	7	2	2	2	10	4	0	8	1	8
44	0.3	0.22	0	8	10	0	4	0	6	3	1	1	1	6	5	0	9	1	7
45	0	0	0.97	0	0	10	6	1	11	12	0	2	2	18	9	1	8	1	8
46	0.25	0.23	0.43	10	10	10	10	1	6	5	1	1	1	7	8	1	9	1	5
47	0.45	0	0.69	10	0	10	8	1	11	9	1	1	1	11	8	0	9	1	6
48	0.25	0	1.04	10	0	10	9	1	11	9	1	2	2	12	9	1	8	1	7
49	0.27	0	0.66	6.67	0	10	7	1	8	7	1	1	1	8	8	1	6	1	6
50	0.32	0.09	0.94	10	10	8.75	8	1	12	7	0	2	2	12	8	1	9	1	8
51	0.27	0.27	2	8.33	10	10	9	1	12	10	1	2	2	13	8	1	7	1	7
52	0.28	0	0	10	0	0	9	0	8	7	2	2	2	9	9	1	8	1	6

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الخلاصة

تهدف هذه الدراسة الى الكشف عن الصعوبات التي يواجهها الطلبة الجامعيون العراقيون الدارسون للغة الانكليزية بوصفها لغة أجنبية في استعمال التركيب المبني للمجهول في اللغة الانكليزية على مستوى التمييز والاداء ، وقد أستندت الدراسة الى الفرضيات الآتية:-

1- يواجه الطلبة الجامعيون العراقيون صعوبات عند استعمال التركيب المبني للمجهول في اللغة الانكليزية ، وتكون هذه الصعوبات تصاعديا على النحو الآتي:-
أ- تحويل مكان الفاعل والمفعول به.
ب- بنية الفعل وكيفية تكوينه.

2- ان وضوح التركيب يتناسب طرديا مع اداء الطلبة على المستويين المذكورين، أي أن أداء الطلبة عند توجيههم مباشرة لاستعمال التركيب المبني للمجهول يكون أفضل منه عندما يكون الاداء تلقائيا، دون حثهم على استعمال التركيب مباشرة، كما في فقرات الاختبار المتعلقة بالتمييز والاداء، وعند كتابة موضوعات الانشاء الموجه.

3- يتناسب اجتناب استعمال التركيب المبني للمجهول في الانشاء التحريري الموجه طرديا مع الصعوبات الكامنة في التركيب والمتمثلة في نتائج الطلبة عند ادائهم لفقرات الاختبار المتعلقة بالتمييز والاداء.

4- ثمة تطور في أداء الطلبة من كلتا المجموعتين وعلى كلا المستويين، مع زيادة في عدد تراكيب المبني للمجهول المستخدمة في الانشاء التحريري الموجه الذي يكتبه الطلبة في المراحل المتقدمة، مقارنة بعدد التراكيب التي ينتجها الطلبة في المراحل الاولى من الجامعة.

5- الاخطاء التي يرتكبها الطلبة في استعمال بنية الفعل والمنسوبة الى التداخل اللغوي، اكثر من تلك التي تعود الى العوامل الاخرى، المؤثرة في اداء الطلبة في هذا المجال.

بعد اجراء مسح شامل لادبيات النحو الانكليزية المتوفر حول الموضوع، صمم اختبار للتحقق من الفرضيات الواردة سابقا، وبناء على اختبار استطلاعي، تم تطبيق هذا الاختبار على ستين طالبا وطالبة (ذكورا واناثا) من قسم اللغة الانكليزية، وتشتمل العينة على ثلاثين طالبا وطالبة من المرحلة الثانية، ومثلهم من المرحلة الرابعة، من قسم اللغة الانكليزية في كلية اللغات من جامعة بغداد، وعند تحليل اجابات الطلبة عن فقرات الاختبار والانشاء التحريري الموجه، طبقت معادلات الاختبار الزائي، معامل ثبات الارتباط، الاختبار التائي، وتحليل التباين، وعليه تم التوصل الى الاستنتاجات الآتية:-

1- يواجه الطلبة العراقيون في المراحل الاولى والمتقدمة من الدراسة الجامعية صعوبات في استعمال التركيب المبني للمجهول في اللغة الانكليزية، اذ ان معرفة التحويل وبنية الفعل يشكلان صعوبة للطلبة اكبر من ادائهم عند توجيههم مباشرة لاستعمال التركيب، بينما تكون

الصعوبة اكبر في اداء بنية الفعل منها في تمييزه، عندما يستعمل الطلبة في المراحل الاولى والمتقدمة هذه التراكيب من غير ايعاز او توجيه.

فضلا عن ذلك ، تكون الصعوبة في استعمال بنية الفعل على كلا المستويين عندما يواجه الطلبة بشكل مباشر وغير مباشر لاداء بنية الفعل، اكبر منها عند استعمال التحويل. اما الطلبة في المراحل المتقدمة، فان اداء التحويل للتراكيب الخاضعة للاختبار يشكل صعوبة اكبر منها في بنية الفعل عند توجيههم مباشرة لاداء هذه التراكيب.

2- ان اداء الطلبة لبنية الفعل المبني للمجهول عند توجيههم مباشرة لاستعمال التركيب افضل منه عند ادائهم للتركيب دون ايعاز، كما هو الحال في ادائهم لبعض فقرات الاختبار على مستوى التمييز والاداء، وكتابة موضوعات الانشاء.

3- لا يتناسب اجتناب الطلبة لاستعمال التركيب المبني للمجهول في كتابة موضوعات الانشاء مع الصعوبة المتمثلة في ادائهم عند تمييز وأداء فقرات الاختبار، اذ ان هذا الاجتناب ينجم عن متغيرات تتعلق بعوامل نفسية، على سبيل المثال ثقة الطالب بمعلومات محدودة عن تركيب معين.

4- هنالك تطور ذو فرق معنوي مهم بين المجموعتين الخاضعتين للاختبار، للمرحلتين الثانية والرابعة، في استخدام التركيب المبني للمجهول وعلى كلا المستويين.

5- ان التأثير السلبي للغة الام (العربية) هو المسؤول عن معظم الاخطاء التي يقع فيها الطلبة في استعمال بنية الفعل، حيث أن معظم الاجابات الخاطئة تتضمن استخدام التركيب المبني للمعلوم بدلا من المبني للمجهول، وحذف الفعل المساعد (يكون) الذي يسبق اسم المفعول في اللغة الانكليزية.

وعلى هذا الاساس، قدمنا عددا من التوصيات والمقترحات التي تتعلق بتدريس اللغة الانكليزية ، والبحوث المستقبلية.

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

وَقُلْ رَبِّ زِدْنِي عِلْمًا

صَدَقَ اللَّهُ الْعَظِيمُ
سُورَةُ طه 114

جامعة بغداد

دراسة تحليلية لل صعوبات التي يواجهها
الطلبة الجامعيون العراقيون الدارسون للغة الانكليزية بوصفها لغة
اجنبية
في استعمال التركيب المبني للمجهول

رسالة مقدمة الى مجلس كلية اللغات – جامعة بغداد
جزءاً من متطلبات درجة الماجستير آداب
في اللغة الانكليزية وعلم اللغة

الطالبة
الحان طارق نجم

باشراف
الاستاذ الدكتور صباح الراوي

تشرين الاول 1999